

Transformation scenarios for boosting organic farming and organic aquaculture towards the Farm-to-Fork targets

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Deliverable D8.7 12 policy briefs

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Document summary

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History of changes

Version 0.1	13/02/2026	Susanne Padel (IFOAM EU), Sabine Reinecke (FiBL CH), Nicolas Lampkin (Thuenen)	Draft
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Version 1	25/02/2026	Boglarka Bozsogi (IFOAM EU)	Submission

Executive Summary

This deliverable D8.7 -12 policy briefs presents the policy briefs developed within the OrganicTargets4EU project. This report summarises the approach and includes summaries of all 12 policy briefs (see overview in Table 1 and background to each brief in Section 1.2. Each brief contains specific recommendations to one policy area.

The current policy context, shaped by the commitment of the Commission to supporting further growth of the organic sector and set by the future Multi-annual Financial Framework (2028-2034), the proposal for a future CAP after 2027 and the anticipated future EU Organic Action Plan will provide many opportunities to support a dynamic development of the organic sector by implementing recommendations both at European and at national level.

The policy briefs themselves are found in

Annex: 12 policy briefs.

Table 1 List of 12 policy briefs with permalinks, authors, and main sources

No.	Title Permalink	Authors	Source
1	Growing organic farming: drivers and barriers https://orgprints.org/56896	Jahl I, Reinecke S (FiBL)	Reinecke et al. (2024)
2	Getting to 25% organic: alternative routes and options https://orgprints.org/56897	Zanoli R (UNIVPM), Mora O (INRAE)	Zanoli et al. (2026)
3	Achieving organic targets: Delivering for the economy and the environment https://orgprints.org/56898	Lampkin N (Thuenen)	Lampkin & Padel (2026, Chapter 2)
4	Future options for organic production and processing: lessons from sector modelling https://orgprints.org/56899	Schiavo M (IDDRI)	Schiavo (2025a), Schiavo (2025b)
5	Organic area support: An environmental priority for all in the next CAP https://orgprints.org/56900	Lampkin N (Thuenen)	Lampkin et al. (2024), Lampkin & Padel (2026, Chapter 3)
6	Closing the organic delivery gap: Policy levers for stronger organic supply chains https://orgprints.org/56901	Zanoli R (UNIVPM), Cisowski F (ITAB), Schiavo M (IDDRI)	Cisowski & Serre J (2024), Lampkin & Padel (2026, Chapter 4), Schiavo (2025b)
7	Building consumer demand for organic food https://orgprints.org/56902	Frank DA, Thøgersen J (AU), Zanoli R (UNIVPM)	Frank et al. (2025), Lampkin & Padel (2026, Chapter 5)
8	Strengthening organic in AKIS: for better advice, training, and knowledge exchange https://orgprints.org/56903	Katalin Szépkuthy Allacherné, ÖMKI	Nagy et al. (2023), Padel et al. (2025), Lampkin & Padel (2026, Chapter 6)
9	Organic research and innovation: a strategic investment in Europe's agri-food systems https://orgprints.org/56904	Moeskops B (IFOAM OE), Padel S (OPBRC), Trkulja (ICROFS)	Gernert et al. (2025), Trkulja et al (2025), Lampkin & Padel (2026, Chapter 7)
10	Does Organic Count? Better statistics and market data https://orgprints.org/56905	Lampkin N (Thuenen)	Lampkin & Padel (2026, Chapter 8)
11	Strengthening organic aquaculture in Europe https://orgprints.org/56906	Lembo G, Toomey L (COISPA)	Lampkin et al. (2024), Lampkin & Padel (2026, Chapter 9)

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12	Organic Action Plans: Integrating policies, building capacity, acting locally https://orgprints.org/56907	Lampkin N (Thuenen)	Lampkin & Padel (2026, Chapter 10)
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1 Introduction

This deliverable presents the policy briefs developed within the OrganicTargets4EU project. The policy briefs are a core deliverable to communicate the output of the project's multi-actor policy dialogue assessing the feasibility of the EU's 25% of farmland organic and a significant expansion of organic aquaculture by 2030 targets in the Farm to Fork Strategy. They provide policy recommendations for the current and future CAP, the EU and national organic action plans, Horizon Europe, and horizontal legislation on inputs, public procurement etc. The policy briefs were produced based on the outcomes of the work carried out in all the work packages of the project, with further analysis and discussion at national and European level in WP7 (see Table 1).

The policy briefs cover all project themes related to the two project strands: production and markets, and knowledge and innovation. Each brief elaborates on thematically focused policy recommendations that cover short-term options within existing policy frameworks (up to 2027), as well as opportunities for policy developments in the next policy reform from 2028 onwards. Where suitable they also horizon scanning for development post 2030 for the whole next multi-annual financial framework to 2034.

The OrganicTargets4EU project identified the following target groups for the development of policy recommendations: (1) individual farmers and aquaculture operators, farmer organisations, aquaculture organisations; (2) input suppliers; (3) organic associations; (4) certification bodies; (5) advisory services and associations; (6) retailers, food business and their associations; (7) environmental groups and NGOs; (8) researchers; (9) policymakers and politicians at national and EU level, and funding bodies. The policy briefs and recommendations primarily target policymakers and politicians at national and EU level, as well as funding bodies policy-engaged researchers, NGOs, organic producer groups and organic associations, advisory services and the organic food sector.

2 Further details of the policy briefs

The topics, authors and the main source of the 12 policy briefs are summarised in Table 1. The policy briefs themselves are found in

Annex: 12 policy briefs.

Table 2 List of 12 policy briefs with permalinks, authors, and main sources

No.	Title Permalink	Authors	Source
1	Growing organic farming: drivers and barriers https://orgprints.org/56896	Jahr I, Reinecke S (FiBL)	Reinecke et al. (2024)
2	Getting to 25% organic: alternative routes and options https://orgprints.org/56897	Zanoli R (UNIVPM), Mora O (INRAE)	Zanoli et al. (2026)
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2.1 Approach

Three of the policy briefs (# 1, 2 and 4) were developed directly on the basis of the results of the relevant work packages (WP1, WP2 and WP3.1/4.4 respectively).

The other nine were based on the results of individual work packages as well as further analysis and consultation in Work Package 7. The relevant chapters of Lampkin & Padel (2026) are indicated in Table 1. The development of these policy recommendations and policy briefs involved:

1. A review of the project outcomes from WP1 to WP6, assessing the relevance of the policy gaps and priorities for action identified related to the two strands of Production and Markets and Knowledge and Innovation. Previous research and relevant policy contexts were also analysed, together with emerging details of the future EU policy environment from 2028.
2. National policy workshops held with stakeholders in seven focus countries and one transnational workshop on the theme of aquaculture.
3. Draft policy recommendations discussed at the Organic Summit in Denmark in August 2025, at the final project conference in Brussels in November 2025, and in interviews with representatives from different parts of the EU Commission.
4. Relevant policies recommendations defined in the context of the current CAP and EU Organic Action Plan (to 2027), as well as the announced proposals to be implemented in the 2028-2034 period.

A detailed description of the approach is provided in Lampkin & Padel (2026, Chapter 1).

2.2 Project background of the policy briefs

Based on review of the project outcomes, key themes were identified which form the basis for the policy briefs, presented here together with the work packages and deliverables on which the policy briefs are based.

1. **Drivers and barriers:** Work Package 1 provided a thorough understanding of diverse factors that drive or hinder the development of the organic sector in the EU countries. It analysed key lessons gained from literature and practical experience in the focus countries, exploring the influence of the farming community, agricultural policy and the food market. The policy brief summarises this long-term system perspective into policy recommendations based primarily on D1.3 Reinecke et al. (2023) Synthesis of key drivers and lock-ins for organic sector development.

2. **Scenarios and backcasting:** Workpackage 2 provides a comprehensive foresight analysis of the pathways and policy options for achieving the European Union's Farm to Fork (F2F) target of 25%. It combines EU-level scenarios with participatory national backcasting to translate the ambition into sequenced actions and identify levers that work across futures. The policy brief develops this further into recommendations for managing a systems transition with the main results in D2.1 Zanolini et al. (2026) Scenarios for the development of the organic sector.
3. **Sector growth projections, target achievability and relevance.** Data on the development of the organic sector historically and during the project have been collected and analysed in several work packages (Tasks 1.4, 2.1, 3.1 and 3.3). Projections of future growth potential have been made using different methods reaching similar conclusions: it is unlikely that the 25% target can be achieved by 2030—15-18% is more likely—but 25% is still conceivable at a later date and targets continue to have value in EU and national policy setting. The topics are developed in Chapter 2 of Lampkin & Padel (2026).
4. **Modelling of production and market trends:** As part of WP 3 and 4 the structural characteristics of both current and future organic and conventional farms across multiple countries and sectors were analysed under two different future scenarios, as well as the processing of specific organic products in value chains in France and Denmark. This was reported in D3.2 Schiavo M (2025a) Socio-economic impact assessment of scenarios, at sectoral and focus country level and D4.3 Schiavo (2025b): Modelling results of socio-economic impacts in the organic value chains. Based on this analysis the policy brief explores potential shifts in structures, employment, investment, and competitiveness in relation to different scenarios of different policy, market, and investment scenarios in different countries.
5. **Organic production support payments,** typically but not exclusively area-based payments for conversion to and maintenance of organic production, as well as interactions with eco-schemes, agri-environment/climate schemes, and alternative options. The topic is mainly addressed in D1.2 Lampkin et al. (2024): Assessment of agricultural and aquaculture policy responses to the organic F2F targets, as well as Chapter 3 of Lampkin & Padel (2026).
6. **Supply chain development,** covering issues relating to retailing, out-of-home catering, public procurement, imports and exports, as well as supply chain co-ordination and co-operation. The topic is mainly addressed in D4.2 Cisowski & Serre (2024) Report on Delphi expert interviews on value chain changes and business strategies and D4.3 Schiavo (2025b) Modelling results of socio-economic impacts in the organic value chains, as well as Chapter 4 of Lampkin & Padel (2026).

7. **Consumer demand** influences, including promotion campaigns and retailer/caterer communications. The topic is mainly addressed in D4.1 Frank et al. (2025) Report on Assortment Change and Active Marketing Effects on Demand Pattern. as well as Chapter 5 of Lampkin & Padel (2026).
8. **AKIS: Advice and mentoring**, including conversion information, technical, environmental and business advice advisor training, group actions, peer-to-peer networks and individual mentoring; **Training and education**, including professional development training for producers, advisors, trainers, inspectors, and others working with food and farming businesses, and education supporting next generation consumers, producers and other professions, in schools, colleges and universities. The topics are mainly addressed in D1.1 Nagy et al. (2023) Assessment of the knowledge and innovation systems for organic agriculture, aqua culture and value chain actors, D1.3 Reinecke et al. (2023): Synthesis of key drivers and lock-ins for organic sector development, and D5.2. Padel et al. (2025) Analysis of barriers of conversion and recommendations for strengthening organic advisory services and capacity building, as well as Chapter 6 of Lampkin & Padel (2026).
9. **Research and innovation**, including applied approaches involving producers and other stakeholders, priority topics and approaches for R&D in general, and co-ordination of organic-specific research funding. This topic is mainly addressed in D5.1 Gernet et al (2025) Strategic Research and Innovation Agenda for Organic Food and Farming, and in D6.1 Trkulja et al. (2025) CORE Organic Pleiades network roadmap to 2030 and EU-level recommendations for better alignment of transnational R&I investments, as well as Chapter 7 of Lampkin & Padel (2026).
10. **Statistics and market data**, which emerged as a key issue in relation to both data for research conducted during the project (e.g., WP3), and the need for farms, food businesses and policymakers to have access to good quality data for investment decision-making and outcome evaluation, as discussed in Chapter 8 of Lampkin & Padel (2026).
11. **Aquaculture** was studied in most parts of the project, but the conclusions have been combined in a single, dedicated policy brief. Policy relevant information is included in D1.2 Lampkin et al., (2024) Assessment of agricultural and aquaculture policy responses to the organic F2F targets, as well as Chapter 9 of Lampkin & Padel (2026).
12. **Organic action plans** and **capacity development** have relevance to all the above themes. Action plans are widely implemented and cover the integration of public good and market policies, including supply-push, demand-pull and knowledge systems, but there is potential for improvement with respect to scope, implementation and evaluation of action plans. Capacity development and bio-districts cover aspects of increasing importance within the organic sector and relevant public institutions. Policy-relevant information is included in D1.2

Lampkin et al., (2024) Assessment of agricultural and aquaculture policy responses to the organic F2F targets, as well as in Chapter 10 of Lampkin & Padel (2026).

3 Conclusions

The OrganicTargets4EU project was set up in support of the EU Farm to Fork and Biodiversity Strategies' aim to reach 25% of agricultural land (UAA) under organic farming and a significant increase in organic aquaculture by 2030.

The project analysed production, market development, knowledge systems and socio-economic and environmental impacts under different scenarios, shaped by policy support, market pull, and citizen action.

Policy recommendations were developed in Work Package 7 using the project results, other literature and engagement with stakeholders at national and European level (see Lampkin and Padel 2026). The context and recommendations were summarised into nine policy briefs linked directly to this report, and three linked to other workpackages.

The current policy context, shaped by the commitment of the Commission to supporting further growth of the organic sector and by the proposed future Multi-annual Financial Framework and CAP after 2027, as well as the anticipated future EU Organic Action Plan, will provide many opportunities to support a dynamic development of the organic sector. The recommendations developed in the project and included in the policy briefs can support this, both at European and at national level.

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Deliverable D8.7
12 policy briefs

Annex: 12 policy briefs

Growing organic farming: drivers and barriers

Introduction

Organic farming is an established part of European agriculture, providing a comprehensive approach that offers practical solutions to numerous EU-wide environmental and socio-economic challenges. It addresses key issues such as soil degradation, biodiversity loss, and climate pressures. By delivering on numerous EU environmental, health, and rural development policy objectives, it contributes to meeting public expectations on sustainable and trustworthy European food.

In 2024, 11.1% of EU agricultural land was managed organically. Although reflecting steady growth, the European Union remains still far from its target to reach 25% of agricultural land managed organically by 2030. Member States vary in their degrees of progress due to context-specific challenges in policy, market, or community. Key challenges such as market fragmentation, limited advisory capacities, or insufficient policy commitment, among others, limit the sector's ability to expand in line with EU ambitions.

This policy brief highlights the key factors driving or constraining organic sector development. By identifying priority areas for actions, it provides the EU and its Member States with evidence on the favourable conditions and levers for advancing towards the 25% target in a meaningful, balanced, and sustainable way.

Key findings

Organic sector development is affected by various drivers and barriers (system lock-ins) rather than singular factors driving the development of organic production and consumption. Sector

Summary

- This policy brief outlines key factors shaping organic sector development in EU Member States.
- Long-term political commitment, targeted market development, and strong knowledge and innovation systems are essential for sustained growth.
- Priority actions to support the sustainable development of the organic sector mix supply-driven strategies with demand-side measures such as market support, diversified retail channels, or public procurement.
- A coherent long-term system approach links policy commitment, strong knowledge systems, and targeted market development to increase both supply and demand for organic products.
- Drawing on the system perspective in this brief, subsequent OrganicTarget4EU policy briefs provide further insight on specific levers for organic sector development.

development depends on how well policy, markets, *and* the farming community work together. Although national contexts differ, progress is strongest where all domains form a coherent, mutually reinforcing system. Organic expansion requires active market and value-chain development, supportive policy frameworks, and well-established institutions in the farming community and AKIS.

System thinking for addressing interdependencies in organic development

From a systems perspective, decisions are shaped not only by economic incentives, regulatory, or support frameworks but also by peer networks, advisory structures, social norms, and perceptions. Figure 1 illustrates this systemic interdependence: Farmers operate at the nexus of the agricultural community, agricultural policy, and the food market.

Figure 1 Key components of a systemic approach to the organic sector

The desire of individual farmers to change their farming practice may be fuelled by a range of disruptive factors, including technical or financial difficulties on the farm, health concerns, or external, e.g., economic, pressures (input prices, market conditions) or environmental factors such as pest and disease pressures or climate change (drought, changed production conditions).

Progress is not achieved through isolated actions, however. Coordinated improvements across all domains are needed. Such a food-system approach also builds alliances with civil society and public actors in related policy areas such as health or education. This strengthens acceptance and creates synergies for sustained development. Looking at sub-system dynamics, the key take aways are:

Policy commitment and continuity are decisive

Commitment to and continuity of support by policymakers are key for organic sector development. Policy commitment is expressed in clear long-term objectives supported by well-funded and stable policy instruments. Support focused mainly on area payments may not create stable market demand. Countries with well-established organic sectors use a mix of supply-push and demand-pull instruments across the value chain, including support for promotion, marketing and processing.

Diverse market channels drive demand

Markets develop best when multiple sales channels operate in parallel. In several EU countries, organic growth has expanded beyond specialised shops to supermarkets, discounters, short food supply chains, and out-of-home catering, improving consumer access and market resilience.

Civil society amplifies legitimacy, awareness, and demand

In countries with advanced organic sectors, civil society, NGOs, and public authorities play a key role in boosting demand. Through public procurement, awareness-raising, and clear communication, they link organic farming to health and sustainability. Ongoing communication, cooperation, and trust-building strengthen acceptance across the value chain boosting consumption

A strong AKIS for organic reduces risk and enables innovation

Reliable information is essential, especially for farmers. AKIS forms a central component in supporting the farming community, linking organic actors—advisory services, training, and research—to both public institutions and market actors. A well-established and visible organic AKIS relies on cooperation between advisory services, training and education providers with organic bodies to effectively link science and practice. Where sustained funding, targeted training, or opportunities for organic research and exchange are lacking, farmers face higher risks, and development slows.

Social norms and peer influence matter

Farmers' conversion decisions are shaped by social factors such as perceived feasibility, perceived risk, and peer influence. Whether organic farming is seen as an appropriate way forward requires confidence in that it is a technically and financially feasible approach, which is strongly influenced by policy or market drivers (support payments, premium prices). However, beyond financial incentives, ideas of "good farming", consumer expectations, access to information and advice (including from peers), social attitudes, and peer pressure all influence risk perception.

Conventional-sector pressures influence decisions

Developments in conventional agriculture strongly affect the organic sector. Organic farming provides opportunities to deliver environmental sustainability, animal welfare, and other public goods. For individual farms, economic pressures and shocks in conventional supply chains—such as the cost-price squeeze—often lead farmers to view organic farming as a more resilient or meaningful alternative.

Policy recommendations

From a food-system perspective, a well-functioning organic sector requires coordinated action across policy, markets, and knowledge systems. With a coherent, long-term systems approach, policymakers can ensure stable conditions for growth that reinforce policy frameworks, strengthen organic AKIS, and support market development:

Build integrated, long-term organic strategies with clear milestones and resources (see also Policy Briefs #3 Targets, #5 Support Payments, and #13 Organic Action Plans)

- Position organic as key response to socio-political challenges reflected consistently across **EU** strategies and regulations, including EU-level guidance and **organic action plans**.
- Coordinate integrated strategies across ministries with clear targets, milestones, and multi-year budgets to anchor organic as a priority for **national** environmental, health, and rural development policies.
- National action plans are stronger where built on strong **civil society** support for organic as well as evidence and stakeholder perspectives.

Strengthen AKIS for organic to reduce risks and support innovation

(see also Policy Brief #8 AKIS)

- Coherent **EU-level** AKIS support provides dedicated funding and stable institutional structures for participatory research, advisory services, training, and farmer-led innovation.
- **Member States** need to integrate organic permanently into vocational training and advisory systems, expanding peer learning, on-farm trials, and demonstration activities.
- Prioritise support for farmer knowledge exchange and **community-based advisory** structures to ensure that knowledge reaches farmers, processors, and other actors effectively.

Develop markets strategically to stabilise demand and diversify access

(see also Policy Briefs #6 Supply chain development, #7 Consumer demand).

- Provide **EU level** policy support for organic processing, distribution, and retail structures, while strengthening guidance on green public procurement for predictable demand.
- Expand processing capacity, regional distribution, and diversified retail channels in **Member States** with national public procurement targets for consistent demand and **consumer** access.
- Support **societal** diversification initiatives that strengthen short supply chains, community-based food initiatives, or transparent communication on organic products. Raise awareness and reinforce consumer trust for stabilised demand.

Strengthen communication, legitimacy, and transparency to build trust in organic

(see Policy brief #7 Consumer demand)

- Simplified and clear **EU** certification rules and EU-wide communication and coordination structures help present organic as a credible and effective policy instrument.
- Strengthen **national-level** communication to promote a positive, solution-oriented narrative on organic highlighting the practical opportunities for farmers, processors, and retailers.
- Develop **community-level** communication and cross-sector alliances that embed organic in society and reinforce its legitimacy by providing independent, accessible information and guidance to value-chain actors.

Further information

All OrganicTargets4EU deliverables: <https://orgprints.org/view/projects/OT4EU.html>.

All OrganicTargets4EU policy briefs: <https://organictargets.eu/policy-briefs/>.

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Getting to 25% organic: alternative routes and options

Introduction

The European Union is committed to a food system that is healthier, more resilient and less dependent on synthetic inputs. Organic farming is one of the few tools that can deliver multiple objectives at once: lower pesticide and nutrient losses, better soil and biodiversity outcomes, and stronger rural value chains. These are important contributions for policymakers concerned with strengthening rural economies, reducing environmental impacts, and keeping EU food systems competitive in a world of input shocks.

Achieving the Farm to Fork target of 25% of EU farmland managed organically by 2030 is about making the transition manageable: balanced supply and demand, enough advisory capacity, and value chains ready to absorb growth. There are different routes that can be taken to get there, whether more environment or market focused.

Achieving the target by whichever route requires a coordinated package that aligns CAP incentives, market development, knowledge systems (AKIS), and demand-side instruments such as public procurement.

Key issues

- Without stable demand signals and investment in advice and value chains, conversion slows, and the sector risks boom-bust cycles.
- Organic supports public goods delivery (climate, biodiversity, pesticide reduction, water security), while contributing to rural employment, value addition, and resilience to input shocks.

Summary

- The Farm to Fork objective of 25% organic land by 2030 can be pursued through different growth pathways shaped by policy support, market pull, and citizen action.
- OrganicTargets4EU combines EU-level scenarios with participatory national backcasting to translate the ambition into sequenced actions and identify levers that work across futures.
- Organic is a policy instrument delivering multiple public goods—climate mitigation and adaptation, biodiversity, soil and water protection, reduced pesticide exposure, nutrition and health, animal welfare and resilient rural economies—but only if supply, demand, and value chains scale together.
- A managed transition reduces the risk of unstable conversion patterns due to the lack of stable demand, uneven national performance and fragmented investment.

Headline policy recommendations:

- **Move from “targets” to “delivery”:** deploy an EU–national **Organic Delivery Package** combining (1) **smart incentives** (CAP + state aid fit-for-purpose), (2) **market pull** (public procurement + value-chain development), and (3) **system enablers** (AKIS, advisory services, R&I, market intelligence/price transparency).
- **Coordinate and monitor:** create or strengthen **organic market observatories** and national **stakeholder platforms** to anticipate bottlenecks and align measures.
- **Use public procurement strategically:** set practical, measurable procurement pathways to stabilise demand and de-risk conversion.

- Organic growth must be managed as a transition—balanced supply and demand, affordable access, and credible monitoring—otherwise public support erodes.

Key findings

OrganicTargets4EU combined EU-level foresight scenarios with participatory national backcasting to test the feasibility of the 25% ambition under different futures. As illustrated in Figure 1, when uncertainty is high and causal relationships are less well established, scenario work (“what if?”) becomes more appropriate than prediction or simple projection based on available data.

The four scenarios developed and evaluated reflect different perspectives on the role of policy support and markets as drivers for organic growth. The Green Public Policy scenario reflects a strong environmental public policy-driven growth, with more growth on arable land. By contrast, the Organic on Every Table scenario assumes strong market engagement from retailers and public and private caterers, building on positive policy support, delivering market-led outcomes that would also favour more production of fruit and vegetables. In light of changing policy priorities in the last few years, the Divergent Pathways scenario reflects different priorities in different countries, with a mix of policy-driven, market-driven or non-interventionist approaches. An alternative Organic Power to the People scenario considers the possibility that organic growth might be driven by citizen action and less by commercial or state interests (see Zanoli et al. 2026 for more information).

Across scenarios—from strong public-policy push and citizen mobilisation to more market-driven or fragmented pathways—progress depends on whether policy aligns three systems at once: (1) CAP-linked incentives for conversion and maintenance, (2) demand and market organisation (including public procurement), and (3) knowledge and innovation systems (AKIS and R&I) that solve conversion bottlenecks. Backcasting shows that sequencing matters: early capacity building and market readiness reduce later instability.

- Robust policy levers across scenarios include stronger AKIS, targeted R&I and innovation uptake, market intelligence/price transparency, stakeholder coordination, and public procurement.
- National pathways differ depending on current national trends and most likely scenarios, but the bottlenecks repeat: advice capacity, value-chain readiness, and weak progress monitoring.
- Best policy hook: manage the transition with milestones to keep markets balanced and avoid boom-bust conversion cycles.

Figure 1. Scenarios as a foresight technique

Development needs and challenges, policy options

Backcasting highlights a practical challenge for policy implementation: current instruments often operate in silos. CAP support can increase organic area, but conversion slows when advisory services are overstretched, when processing and logistics are missing, or when retailers and public buyers do not provide stable demand. Likewise, demand-promotion can backfire if supply cannot respond, leading to imports, price spikes, and political backlash.

Three development needs stand out. First, stronger steering through milestones: progress tracking should combine hectares with market indicators (processing capacity, procurement volumes, price signals, AKIS capacity). Second, stronger knowledge capacity: AKIS must deliver practical support on conversion, resilience and value-chain adaptation. Third, stronger governance: organic growth depends on coordinated action across ministries, regions and private actors; ad-hoc coordination leaves gaps and slows delivery. These needs are not additional bureaucracy. They are the prerequisites for a managed transition that protects farmer confidence, stabilises markets, encourages investment, and maintains public trust.

Policy options (robust across scenarios)

The foresight analysis of OrganicTargets4EU identifies options that remain relevant across different futures. They work because they link supply, demand and knowledge, and they can be implemented within existing frameworks while building a pathway to 2030:

- Scale demand certainty via public procurement (schools, hospitals, public canteens) with clear criteria and multi-year purchasing commitments.
- Strengthen AKIS: Research & Innovation, advisory services, training and demonstration focused on conversion bottlenecks and resilience.

Why does this differ from 'more conversion payments'?

Because it treats organic growth as a managed transition: it makes demand visible, scales knowledge capacity early, and uses market indicators to change course before crises appear. Scenario and backcasting evidence suggest translating ambition and quantitative targets into sequencing and accountability—rather than hoping dispersed measures add up by 2030:

- Target R&I and innovation uptake (including processing and value-chain innovation) aligned with national needs.
- Improve market intelligence and price/volume transparency; use early-warning indicators to avoid boom-bust cycles of organic conversion without a stable demand growth.
- Build coordination platforms and a progress dashboard that links CAP implementation, organic action plans and market development.

Policy recommendations

Adopt a coordinated 'Organic Transition Package' delivering on multiple public goods with milestones to 2030

Create one joined-up package per Member State (e.g., in Organic Action Plans) that aligns CAP supports, market development, and knowledge actions, tracked with milestones (see also policy briefs #1 Drivers and #13 Action plans)

- **EU policymakers:** provide a common milestone framework (hectares + market indicators), develop incentives for public good delivery and enable peer learning between Member States.

- **National policymakers:** integrate milestones into CAP Strategic Plan implementation and organic action plans; assign clear governance and a single progress dashboard.
- **NGOs:** convene multi-actor coalitions, monitor delivery, and communicate progress in accessible narratives that sustain political commitment.

Make demand predictable: scale public procurement and mainstream channels

Use purchasing power and clear market signals to stabilise the transition and improve affordability (see also policy brief # 7 Consumer demand).

- **EU policymakers:** strengthen guidance and funding support for sustainable food procurement with organic sourcing criteria.
- **National policymakers:** set measurable procurement targets (schools, hospitals, public canteens) and use multi-year contracts to give suppliers confidence.
- **NGOs:** support implementation (training for procurers, model tenders) and connect organic to health and local value creation in public communication.

Strengthen AKIS and targeted R&I to remove conversion bottlenecks

Invest in advice, training, demonstration and innovation uptake so farms and value chains can convert and stay resilient (see also policy brief #8 AKIS).

- **EU policymakers:** prioritise organic-relevant advisory and innovation actions in Horizon Europe, EIP-AGRI, and knowledge networks.
- **National policymakers:** ring-fence funding for organic advisory services, training and demonstration farms, linked to identified national bottlenecks.
- **NGOs:** co-deliver peer learning and feed practitioner needs into research agendas and policy dialogues.

Build market transparency and risk management into organic growth

Use data and early-warning indicators to anticipate over- or undersupply, protect farm viability, and maintain public trust (see also policy briefs #6 Supply chains & #7 Consumer demand).

- **EU policymakers:** support EU-level market observatories and harmonised reporting on prices, volumes, and trade for organic products.
- **National policymakers:** publish market data, promote fair contracting practices including pluriannual tripartite contracts (farmers, processors, retailers), and use monitoring to adjust CAP implementation in real time.
- **NGOs:** share market intelligence with members, promote transparency across supply chains, and flag emerging risks early to policymakers.

Further information

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Raffaele Zanoli, UNIVPM, Olivier Mora, INRAE, January 2026

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Achieving organic targets:

Delivering for the economy and the environment

Introduction

Organic farming delivers on two main areas of EU policy: **environmental public goods** by adapting production practices and restricting certain inputs, and **economic and employment benefits** for rural areas through specialist organic markets.

In recognition, organic farming is supported in the EU by legal definition since 1992 and by area support for organic conversion and maintenance introduced as a CAP agri-environmental measure in 1994.

The 2020 Farm to Fork and Biodiversity Strategies set a range of ambitious environmental targets, including achieving 25% of the EU agricultural area managed organically, and a significant increase in organic aquaculture, by 2030.

Supported by the 2021 EU Organic action plan, the targets and policy goals were integrated into Member State CAP Strategic Plans for 2023-2027 and national organic action plans covering periods up to 2030.

In the current CAP, 5% of total financial resources (20% of environmental funds) are budgeted to provide support for organic conversion and maintenance to reach 10% of EU agricultural area (UAA) under organic by 2027. As not all organic land is supported, this is likely to be equivalent to about 15% of UAA certified as organic or in-conversion.

The CAP and national organic action plans implemented in almost all EU member states represent a material enhancement of organic policy ambition in the EU from 2023. If successful, EU organic farming could grow by 10 Mha, up from 15 Mha or 9% of UAA in 2020. This is still some way from achieving the EU's 25% target, or Member States' organic action plan targets averaging 18%, by 2030, indicating that further policy actions are required to deliver the ambition.

Summary

The EU has set ambitious targets for organic farming to reach 25% of its agricultural area by 2030 and for a significant increase in organic aquaculture.

Progress towards the target is steady, with the organic land area share increasing from 9% in 2020 towards 12% in 2025, but the target of 25% is not likely to be achieved—15%-18% by 2030 is more likely, 25% by 2035 is conceivable.

Achieving the targets would have significant impacts on organic production, rural economy, and the environment, benefiting European citizens, not just organic consumers.

Growth in market and land area share has, however, stalled in many countries following the pandemic and the war in Ukraine. Putting the organic sector back on a recovery path is a key policy priority.

The 2028-2034 CAP provides an opportunity to implement coherent policies to support transformative organic sector growth.

Continued commitment to appropriate land area and market shares and environmental targets is critical for this process.

Key findings

The OrganicTargets4EU project tracked the development of organic farming in the EU and its member states since the 1980s¹. Since 2000, the organic land area has doubled every ten years, while the market trebled.

Growth of certified organic and in-conversion land area (Mha) and share (%) of utilisable agricultural area (UAA) in the European Union, 2000-2024 (Source: data from FIBL Statistics)

A continuation of these growth trends would imply 18% UAA organic by 2030, and 25% by 2035. A more modest linear projection based on the last CAP 2014-2022 would reach 15% by 2030. Trend impact analysis underpinning the scenarios analysed in the project and a logistic growth curve model used for CAPRI modelling yielded similar results. These do not, however, account for the impacts of increased emphasis on organic farming policy in the CAP Strategic Plans and national organic action plans from 2023, which could drive faster growth. The projections are complicated by a slowdown in organic market growth in 2022-23, due to a combination of the Covid pandemic and the food price inflation following the war in Ukraine. Although 2023 and 2024 data show clear signs of the organic market growing again, a slowdown in new conversions and reversions to conventional production in some countries have impacted on the land area growth rates in 2024. Data for 2025 are not yet available.

The response varied by country. Several with long-established organic markets such as France, Germany, Austria, Sweden, and Denmark have experienced slow growth or small declines in sales and certified organic land area. Others such as Bulgaria, Ireland, Greece, Portugal, and Romania have seen much more rapid growth. Typically, these countries build from a lower starting point with more generous support programmes introduced or are focused on exports with less domestic sales.

Impacts of achieving the 25% UAA organic target

Modelling work in the project looked at EU-wide impacts using the CAPRI tool and specific sector impacts in individual countries using an impact-output simulation tool developed by IDDRI. These considered different scenarios for EU organic policy and market development to 2030.

¹ For more details, see the World of Organic Agriculture reports <https://statistics.fibl.org/index.html> and the OrganicTargets4EU national organic sector factsheets <https://organictargets.eu/organic-sector-factsheets/>.

The CAPRI modelling found that while overall output and incomes would decline, income reductions could be covered by organic support payments and premium prices—it was not possible to model the organic market specifically using this tool. The CAPRI modelling also identified good potential for environmental impacts, thanks to reduced nitrogen fertiliser and pesticide use, reduced greenhouse gas emissions, and more biodiversity-friendly farming practices

The IDDRi modelling identified potential for rural employment and incomes to be increased, but it was unlikely that the organic sector would be immune to general trends towards larger farm sizes.

Targets and policy challenges

Given the uncertainty over whether EU's targets can be achieved, it is tempting to conclude that they have failed and are therefore valueless. This would be a mistake, for several reasons:

- The latest data available EU wide relate to 2024. There are still six years to go until 2030 with higher support payments planned in some countries and a new CAP programming period with refreshed EU and national organic action plans to come.
- Aspirational targets, even if not achievable, have an important signposting role, as can be seen from the current CAP Strategic Plans and MS national targets. The EU targets and organic action plan were important motivators for some governments to introduce or significantly increase policy support for organic farming and to set their own ambitious targets.
- Realistic targets are important to ensure resources are available to meet demand and to evaluate progress. For the first time, the national CAP Strategic Plans for all EU member states have included budgeted plans for organic expansion. Clear targets and policy support commitments also provide a strong signal to market actors to invest in the organic sector.
- Land area targets alone may not be sufficient. Environmental and market targets could help keep the focus on core policy impacts, as recommended by the European Court of Auditors. Crop diversity, stocking rate and input use indicators could be used as proxies for measuring environmental outcomes directly. Market targets could include shares of retail sales, exports, and public procurement or out-of-home catering.
- In the absence of targets, there is no basis for the evaluation of achievements and policy modifications to address shortfalls or unintended consequences. The recent dropping of targets in Sweden and France, the two countries with declining organic sectors, may further increase the lack of confidence among farmers and market actors to engage with organic.

Previous research on organic action plans has highlighted the importance of targets in setting a context for the actions to be developed and their contribution to organic sector development (growth, competitiveness, and sustainability) (see Policy Brief #13 Organic action plans).

Policy recommendations

Despite the recent challenges, there is still scope for policy to influence recovery and future development, delivering economic and environmental benefits. We recommend the EU Commission should:

Provide strong encouragement and guidance to national governments to a) continue with and enhance organic support in the 2023-2027 CAP Strategic Plans, b) address the recent slowdown in market growth and conversion rates and c) prepare ambitious plans for the transformative development of the sector in the 2028-2034 programming period, by:

- Requesting member states to report soon on plans to upgrade their organic policy measures for 2026-27 to address the slowdown in growth that has been experienced in many countries.
- Maintaining the commitment to 25% of EU agricultural area organic, but by 2035 not 2030.
- Preparing an updated EU-level organic action plan as a basis for providing guidance to national governments as well as supporting mechanisms for sharing best practice in organic policymaking, utilising the EU CAP Network where appropriate.
- Using the recommendations in the OrganicTargets4EU policy briefs as a basis for specific guidance and recommendations to Member States on different policy options and their integration in revised national organic action plans for 2028-2034.

Encourage national governments to continue to set meaningful land area, environmental, and market targets for the development of organic food and farming by 2035, which:

- Define clear policy ambition and direction, informed by stakeholders,
- Recognise the contribution that organic food and farming can make to broader policy goals,
- Are integrated in future CAP plans, organic action plans and other strategies,
- Relate appropriately to production, markets, and environment,
- Are resourced adequately to achieve delivery in relevant timescales,
- Are owned by appropriate agencies to ensure delivery,
- Are monitored and evaluated to ensure the effectiveness of policy implementation, supported by improvements in statistical data collection and reporting (see policy brief #10).

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Nicolas Lampkin, Thünen Institute, January 2026

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Future options for organic production and processing: lessons from sector modelling

Introduction

Growing the organic sector is a cornerstone of the EU's strategies and vision for the sustainable development of the agri-food sector. Farm-processor relationships are a critical driver of sector performance, competitiveness, and value chain development. However, they often remain overlooked in policy development, also because organic farms are often misunderstood as homogeneous, which limits options for making use of processing as an engine for growth. This policy brief presents the results of a sector modelling exercise in the [OrganicTargets4EU](#) project, which analysed organic production and processing structures in selected countries and sectors under different future scenarios.

The case studies covered **dairy, chickens for meat, arable crops, vegetables, wine, and aquaculture**. The modelling explored impacts of alternative policy and market scenarios on the:

- **structure of farms**
- **processing industry**
- **employment**
- **investment.**

Better understanding interlinkages in production and food processing can inform the design of more coherent policies for fair transitions, increased competitiveness, and innovation in the agri-food sector.

Summary

This policy brief examines how organic production and processing systems evolve under different policy, market, and investment scenarios in different countries. It explores potential shifts in structures, employment, investment, and competitiveness in relation to different scenarios.

Key insights for sector development:

- **Organic farms and processors are highly diverse**, and uniform policies risk a too narrow focus
- **Different growth paths across farms and processors** create distinct labour, investment, and structural challenges
- **Data gaps remain a barrier** for tailored policies

Key policy recommendations:

- Support organic farm expansion and conversion
- Provide training and advice for value chain actors
- Strengthen data quality
- Promote stable value chain relations (e.g., long-term producer-processor-distributor contracts).

Key findings

On the **production side**, policies need to adequately account for the diversity among organic farms and their differences from conventional approaches. Ignoring this heterogeneity and variance risk supporting only a subset of farms, undermining overall sectoral development.

Farm characteristics

- Organic farms vary in size, production type, geographical location, and marketing channels (e.g., integrated in conventional supply chains, direct sales, or local markets).
- Organic farms are more labour-intensive, especially in livestock systems, due to smaller size, additional operations, and direct sales or on-farm processing.
- Income per family farm worker in organic systems is generally comparable to or higher than conventional farms.

Future organic farm pathways: i) larger farms with economies of scale, ii) smaller specialised farms focusing on direct marketing, iii) livestock farms with higher welfare standards, iv) mixed crop-livestock systems, and v) farms developing non-agricultural activities such as ecotourism.

Implications of the expansion of organic farming: It increases agricultural labour demand and the number of farms, while overall farm populations may decline due to concentration and productivity gains. The need to hire external labour and complication in farm logistics adds to the reluctance to convert, whereas organic farmers may also hesitate to expand workforce, rather opting for reduced farm or herd size. Such downsizing could increase fixed costs and create stranded assets.

On the **processing side**, the distinct contribution as well as structural difference between organic and conventional, is frequently overlooked. Failing to account for variation in product portfolios, processing approaches, or value-chain actors may lead to inaccurate sector policies.

Livestock processing industry dynamics (chickens/dairy):

- Organic processing differs from conventional production in product types, strategies, and actors involved.
- Labour-intensive on-farm processing for direct sales may create additional employment, partially offsetting job losses in industrial processing
- Regular downgrading organic to conventional, limited exports, and lack of genetic and product innovation limit sector growth.

Future processing pathways

- **Market-driven scenario:** favourable to organic farming, large, integrated firms can increase the processing of organic products to increase the range of products available to consumers, partly offsetting job losses from potentially reduced meat consumption.
- **Policy-driven scenario:** livestock relocation to less densely populated areas processed by smaller, labour-intensive firms may mitigate job losses.

Finally, **data availability** remains a key constraint. Limited information on farm structures, labour requirements, and processing flows hinders the design of targeted policies, making it difficult to fully capture the diversity and operational realities of organic systems (see policy brief #10 Statistics and Market Data).

Case Study: Chickens for meat sector in France

Chickens for meat farming in France is mainly found in the West, especially in Brittany and Pays de la Loire. Farms vary in size, production methods, and sales channels. Organic chickens for meat farms are usually smaller and may sell directly or through other outlets. They raise chickens outdoors for longer periods and use organic feed. In the future, organic production may diversify, with some larger farms meeting growing demand and mixed crop-livestock (MCL) farms combining chickens with arable production (cf. Figure).

The processing industry includes large slaughterhouses, smaller regional plants, on-farm units for direct-sellers, and further processing facilities. Conventional products dominate in high-volume cuts and processing. Organic meat chickens are mainly sold whole and fresh under quality labels, which limits their use in processed products. They are also more often handled by small regional plants or on-farm units.

AI generated sample image: direct chicken marketing

Current Organic Farms

Future Organic Farms

Figure 1. Characteristics of current vs. future organic farms in French chicken meat sector

Contrasting visions for organic growth may have different impacts on farms and processing sectors:

- **Market-driven** scenarios: organic expansion concentrated in large, vertically integrated farms connected to major slaughterhouses and retailers
- **Policy-driven** scenarios: public measures encourage livestock relocation, increased feed autonomy, and development of smaller organic holdings across diverse regions.

Policy recommendations

National and regional support policies should focus on specific sector development needs

- Recognise the impacts of current economic conditions and existing organic support policies (see Policy Brief #5 Organic support payments) on different types of farms, which, depending on region, size, or market opportunities, may face higher costs to convert or maintain organic production.
- Utilise the opportunities provided by the proposed transition lump-sum payment in the next CAP (2028-2034) to support investment in farming, processing, and market development (see Policy Brief #5 Organic support payments).
- Provide incentives and technical assistance for labour management, targeting family-run farms that may face problems hiring additional workers or increasing workloads.
- Invest in more comprehensive market data, e.g., by increasing the samples of organic farms in FADN, and by including volumes of organic products by processing site (see Policy Brief #10 Statistics and Market data).
- Include training and advice for buyers and processors of organic products, including retailers and caterers, to better understand the opportunities and constraints associated with individual organic products and sectors (see Policy Brief #8 AKIS).
- Address constraints within value chains for organic products, including opportunities such as public procurement to better utilise by-products, producer-processor-distributor contracts, and appropriate margins for organic products at processor, distributor, and retailer levels (see Policy Brief #6 Supply Chain Development).

Further information

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Michele Schiavo, IDDRI

January 2026

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Organic support payments: An environmental priority for all in the next CAP

Introduction

Organic farming delivers on two main areas of EU policy: **environmental public goods** by adapting production practices and restricting certain inputs, and **economic and employment benefits** for farmers and rural areas through specialist organic markets. In recognition, organic farming is supported in the EU by legal definition since 1992 and by area payments for organic conversion and maintenance introduced as a CAP agri-environmental measure in 1994.

In the current CAP (2023-2027), organic support payments are foreseen in all national CAP Strategic Plans: 10% of EU agricultural area (UAA) is planned to be supported as organic by 2027, using 5% of the total CAP budget (20% of the environmental support) for the 5-year period. Member states can use Pillar 1 eco-schemes or Pillar 2 environment-climate measures for this support.

The [OrganicTargets4EU](#) project analysed planned support in the national CAP strategic plans and compared it with support available 2014 to 2022.

In the proposal for the next CAP (2028-2034), organic farming is one of six environmental priorities (Art. 4 of Proposal 2025/0241(COD)). Member States must implement agri-environmental-climate support schemes for organic farming (Art. 10.1a). Lump-sum transition funding (Art 10.1b) can support conversion-related investments in advice, training and capital expenditure. Organic farming is also de facto compliant with Farm Stewardship requirements for soil and water conservation if the full holding is certified (Art. 3.6).

Key findings

The planned conversion and maintenance support for organic farming in the current CAP was analysed for all Member States based on their national CAP strategic plans and compared with the previous CAP period (2014-2022). Wide variations in payment bases (e.g., land use categories like arable land or individual crops/livestock), and amounts (e.g., for arable crops, see Figure 1) were identified.

Summary

Organic conversion and maintenance payments have been implemented as agri-environmental measures since 1994 and played a significant role in the growth of organic farming in the EU.

This support will be continued in the next CAP (2028-2035), with organic farming identified as an environmental priority and all Member States required to provide support.

The support recognises the environmental benefits of organic land management. Combinations with other agri-environmental-climate measures help to reinforce this.

The implementation of this support is challenging due to the linked market focus of organic systems, which should not undermine the environmental outcomes. Unintended impacts on the organic market should also be avoided, as the market plays a key role in securing long-term engagement by farmers, underpinning environmental gains.

Additional costs, lack of access to organic premium prices, and restructuring investments during conversion justify higher support levels. The transition lump-sum funding proposed for the next CAP could be a valuable innovation.

Organic farming is attractive to young farmers and new entrants. Support targeting these groups, including the proposed Generational Renewal Strategy, should ensure the organic option is part of the solution.

Figure 1: Maintenance payments for arable crops in 2018 (first column) and 2023 (second column). Variation covers minimum to maximum payment level and may be due to regional, crop and other factors. Source: Lampkin et al. (2024)

Eligibility and other conditions also varied widely, including exclusions of certain land uses and part-organic farms, or reduced/capped payments for larger farms, and constraints on combinations with other eco-schemes or agri-environment-climate measures¹.

There are also wide variations in the share of agricultural area supported as organic, and the proportion of certified organic land that is not supported (see Figure 2). At EU level, about one-third of organic land was not supported in 2018. If planned supported areas (10% of UAA) are achieved and the unsupported share is maintained to 2027, about 15% of UAA may be certified organic or in-conversion at that point.

Figure 2: Share of UAA supported as organic in 2018, certified but not supported in 2018, and planned to be supported in 2027. Columns with no blue bars indicate that 2027 support plans were for lower areas than were certified organic in 2018, the numbers indicate the percentage difference. Source: Lampkin et al. (2024)

¹ Results for the main land uses (grassland, arable, vegetables, fruit, olives, grapes) in individual countries are summarised in the national organic sector factsheets. <https://organictargets.eu/organic-sector-factsheets/>

Development needs and policy challenges

There is a clear focus on organic farming as an environmental measure in the current and future CAP. A key challenge for administrations implementing the organic support is getting the right balance between the environmental outcomes and possible market impacts. The focus on **environmental outcomes** can be strengthened by using indicator-based frameworks, sustainability benchmarking or similar approaches². Better compatibility with other eco-schemes and agri-environment-climate measures can also help to achieve synergies. High double-funding deductions, or higher payments for options that are not combinable with organic, should be avoided to not deter organic scheme participation.

If policymakers are more focused on **market outcomes**, they may conclude that payments can be discontinued when the market is strong or are not worth making if the market is weak. Requirements on producers to market products as organic to qualify for the payments may be enforced. These approaches can be disruptive to market development and result in environmental outcomes not being delivered. Long gaps between successive funding rounds or highly differentiated payments for individual crops can also be problematic. At the same time, generous payments encouraging high uptakes may create supply surpluses and undermine market development.

The assumption made in calculating organic support payments, that **organic premium prices** can offset yield reductions and production cost increases can be problematic. The costs of accessing organic markets also need to be considered, as this is not guaranteed. This can result in organic farmers receiving lower payments than non-organic farmers for the same actions. Premium prices may be better interpreted as a return to the marketing activities undertaken, supporting long-term engagement with organic farming, but not as compensation for environmental outcomes.

The differentiation between conversion and maintenance payments is intended to take account of **higher costs during conversion** due to system restructuring, skills and experience gathering, and the lack of access to premium prices during the conversion period. Some countries make no differentiation between the schemes; others provide a small uplift of 10 or 20%. These limited differences do not fully account for the costs and income forgone faced by farmers during conversion—effectively a lower intervention rate for these payments. This is often justified in terms of not making the conversion payment too attractive and stimulating an unsustainable level of interest. However, it can also deter farmers from converting.

The **lumpsum transition funding** mechanism proposed for the next CAP envisages a payment of up to €200,000 per farm, to cover advice and training as well as capital investments in buildings, machinery, and breeding livestock. If designed appropriately, this could prove attractive for farmers, as restructuring costs can be a major deterrent to conversion, especially for pig and poultry producers. It remains to be clarified how this funding could be integrated with the organic farming maintenance payments.

Several countries show that organic farming can be attractive for **young farmers and new entrants** to agriculture. In Portugal, Next Generation Covid recovery funding to encourage new entrants, prioritising organic farming, resulted in a dramatic uptake in 2021. The Commission proposals for support for young/new farmers and a Generational Renewal Strategy (Proposal 2025/0241 Arts. 14 & 15) could support this, particularly if organic farming is prioritised, or the funding integrated with organic area support.

² Eurochoices special issue, January 2026: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/toc/1746692x/2025/24/3>

Policy recommendations

In reviewing their current support payments, and preparing the support measures from 2028, Member States should focus on environmental outcomes whilst considering the organic market context and supporting the next generation of farmers.

Strengthen the focus on rewarding environmental outcomes from organic farming, by:

- Defining and quantifying the anticipated environmental outcomes
- Developing support that links payments to the extent of environmental outcomes delivered
- Identifying the minimum support levels necessary to encourage organic growth
- Enabling effective combinations with other environmental measures to top-up delivery
- Determining regional, land use, and farm size payment differentiation based on anticipated environmental outcomes, not other factors that might be market-distorting
- Engaging with water agencies and climate and biodiversity organisations to develop partnership approaches to rewarding the environmental outcomes.

Consider the market context and impacts of organic support payments to minimise negative impacts, by:

- Providing a stable support base that allows for development in response to market signals
- Excluding organic premium prices from income forgone calculations, recognising them **instead** as a reward for investments in marketing initiatives
- Avoiding support payment variability and availability delays that can be market distorting
- Avoiding requirements to market products as organic to qualify for payments, or the modification of payments to manage supply and demand

Prioritise organic farming as an option for new entrants and young farmers, by:

- Highlighting the opportunities and the potential environmental and market benefits
- Supporting potential organic producers with getting access to land, including making publicly owned land available on a preferential basis
- Ensuring that the starter-packs and other resources appropriately address the organic option

Further information

Lampkin N & Padel S (2026). *Policy recommendations for the delivery of the organic F2F targets by 2030 and beyond*. Deliverable D7.1 OrganicTargets4EU. IFOAM Organics Europe. <https://orgprints.org/id/eprint/10862>.

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Nicolas Lampkin, Thünen Institute, January 2026

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Closing the organic delivery gap: Policy levers for stronger organic supply chains

Introduction

Europe can hit 25% organic area in 2030 and still fall short on what policymakers and organic stakeholders and citizens actually desire: resilient food supply, lower food waste, credible green claims, and competitive rural value chains. Organic is not just a farming choice—it also applies to supply chain development.

Organic growth is constrained not by farm willingness alone, but also by value-chain frictions in planning, logistics, processing capacity, and fair risk-sharing. When processors cannot place the full product-mix, when retailers keep margins high, or when public catering buys “green” without clear standards, organic producers face volatile demand and the quiet killer: downgrading to conventional outlets and prices. Perishable food chains are especially exposed: weak cold-chain and fragmented logistics turn organic premiums into waste and volatility.

Organic farming’s delivery of public goods is supported particularly by transparent, coordinated, and investable downstream markets. The current focus of support strategies on area targets and farm payments underestimates the importance of the missing middle (processors, retailers, catering), margins and bargaining power, and infrastructure for storage, aggregation, and digital logistics.

Key findings

Experts converge on a pragmatic agenda. Results from the [OrganicTargets4EU](#) Delphi survey show voluntary actions alone will not scale organic. Experts favour the regulation of green claims (see policy brief #7 Consumers), making market margins visible, using public procurement with criteria or targets for organic as a stable demand anchor, and integrating these with targeted CAP and investment support; lower VAT rates on organic products were also raised.

Summary

- The current focus on area-based targets and support underestimates the importance of how value chains can constraint sector growth through weak coordination, limited processing and aggregation capacity, and lack of transparency.
- If markets cannot absorb added supply reliably, demand signals are uncertain, logistics are fragmented, and organic products risk downgrading to conventional. If margins are squeezed, and investments in conversion become harder to justify, especially for smaller operators.
- Levers for supply sector development include creating a market pull, improve fairness in contracts, margins and risk sharing, invest in processing and aggregation, especially for perishable fresh and livestock products, and improve coordination and data sharing.
- Closing these “delivery gaps” is essential for organic sector growth as well as reaching wider policy goals—competitiveness, rural development, health, climate and biodiversity.

Collaboration is still too weak where it matters most. Research on organic supply chains finds low collaboration—especially on cost-benefit sharing—while more integrated chains collaborate more on decision synchronisation. Risk management is a strong trigger for closer coordination.

Margins and bargaining power can block conversion. The Delphi survey and prior studies indicate that higher downstream margins on organic products can push up consumer prices and/or squeeze farmgate prices, weakening both consumer demand and farmers’ willingness to convert. Credible price and volume commitments are therefore essential to encourage organic conversion.

Market-pull works when targeted. Modelling confirms that demand shocks and product-mix bottlenecks create downgrading and stop-start investment. Targeted public procurement and smarter assortment strategies can absorb hard-to-place volumes and stabilise the chain.

Perishability is often a structural constraint. In organic fruit and vegetables, but also dairy chains, time-sensitive logistics and storage capacity often determine market access. Aggregation centres, cold-chain investments and digital matching tools reduce waste and transaction costs—especially for small and mid-size producers.

Innovation must fit organic identity. Innovation uptake depends on acceptability across the whole chain; “unnatural” innovations face strong resistance, while welfare- and resource-efficiency innovations gain support. Co-design and transparency matter as much as technology.

Five levers for the development of organic supply chains¹

¹ Authors’ elaboration based on:
 Naspetti S, et al. (2011). ‘Organic Supply Chain Collaboration: A Case Study in Eight EU Countries’. *Journal of Food Products Marketing* 17 (1-2): 141-62. <https://orprints.org/id/eprint/21645/>;
 Nicholas P et al. (2014). Innovations in low input and organic dairy supply chains – what is acceptable in Europe? *Building Organic Bridges* (Vol. 4, pp. 1167–1170). https://doi.org/10.3220/REP_20_1_2014;
 Kowalska & Bieniek (2022). ‘Meeting the European Green Deal Objective of Expanding Organic Farming’. *Equilibrium. Quarterly Journal of Economics and Economic Policy* 17(3):607–33. <https://doi.org/10.24136/eq.2022.021>;
 OrganicTargets4EU reports Cisowski & Serre (2024) and Schiavo (2025) (see Further information).

Development needs and challenges

Research points to six practical development needs:

- **Stable demand anchors:** stringent criteria and targets for public procurement and predictable contracts that reduce conversion risks.
- **Transparent and fair markets:** fairer margins and stronger checks on misleading green claims.
- **Better chain coordination:** shared demand forecasting, joint planning and data exchange across actors, allowing volumes alignment with market demand.
- **Fit-for-purpose processing and aggregation:** capacity that matches organic volumes and product-mix, preventing downgrading.
- **Logistics infrastructure** for perishable organic goods: storage, cooling, aggregation points, and digital inventory tools to reduce post-harvest loss.
- **Innovation and skills that protect trust:** co-designed R&I and advisory support aligned with organic principles.

Policy recommendations

The market for organic products has been important for the sector's development since the 1990s, supported by a clear legal basis in the EU organic regulations. With many benefits from organic farming accruing to society at large, continued public investment in the sector is justified. This must be balanced with the market's capacity to sustain long-term engagement, with benefits for farmers, consumers, and society at large (see also policy briefs #1 Drivers and barriers and #7 Consumers).

The aim for organic value chain development should be to create and strengthen diverse marketing channels reaching a wide range of consumers and citizens in line with organic values and principles.

Support investment in the development of organic processing and marketing infrastructure

- **EU/national policymakers:** prioritise investment support for organic processing and marketing facilities, farm shops, catering, agritourism with favourable eligibility (including for transition) focused on livestock (suitable scale and locations) and cold chains for perishables and fresh produce.
- **EU policymakers/national actors:** support supply chain aggregation and logistic hubs, producer groups accessing local retail and catering, and transnational networks of organic processing facilities and slaughterhouses using the European Competitiveness Fund.

Strengthen the transparency and efficiency of organic supply chains for quality and affordability

- **EU/national policymakers:** support organic producer organisations (CMO Reg.), co-operatives, and supply chain integration involving organic organisations in co-designing to scale.
- **National actors:** encourage secure, longer-term contracting and supply agreements to rebalance risks, improve traceability, secure producer incomes, and encourage fair cost sharing (e.g., through piloting margin dashboards), improve market development capacity in the organic sector to enable effective collaboration with retailers and processors of organic food and strengthen organic principles in value chains.

Exploit public procurement to grow demand for organic food and citizen engagement

- **EU policymakers:** review Green Public Procurement guidelines and use the EU CAP Network to share best practice, develop common monitoring principles to showcase the value of organic food, and develop appropriate criteria for the use of certified organic products with verifiable sustainability impacts compatible with product sourcing regulations.
- **National policymakers:** encourage the use of organic food in public procurement, with clear threshold targets (e.g., Bronze, Silver, Gold), advice and training for actors, procurement pilots and best practice handbooks for schools and hospitals.

Encourage regional marketing, short supply chains, and bio-districts, more directly linking producers and consumers

- **EU policymakers:** encourage MS to develop bio-districts and regional action plans to develop local organic markets including for gastronomy and agritourism.
- **National policymakers:** support more diverse marketing channels similar to public procurement.

Enable organic suppliers to engage with intra-EU and international trade

- **EU policymakers:** encourage a focus on organic in export initiatives and trade agreements.
- **National policymakers:** support organic in export promotion (trade fairs, international marketing action, cross-border exchanges), potentially using the proposed European Competitiveness Fund, and provide information on compliance issues (organic and customs).

Improve the availability and quality of organic market information and data to support decision-making in business and policy and encourage new investment in the sector

- **EU policymakers:** collate data from organic projects (outcomes, best practice examples), possibly using the EU CAP Network, support the development of relevant interoperable data collection standards and coordination projects (see policy brief #10) and institutional capacity development such as market observatories (policy brief #12).
- **National policymakers:** encourage the participation of value chain actors in AKIS (policy brief #8).

Further information

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Schiavo M. (2025). *Modelling results of socio- economic impacts in the organic value chains*. Deliverable D4.3 OrganicTargets4EU. IFOAM Organic Europe. <https://orgprints.org/id/eprint/56759>

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Building consumer demand for organic food

Introduction

Increasing demand for organic food is a key lever for reaching the EU's 25% organic production target. This requires demand-side action alongside facilitating organic production. In 2023, retail sales of organic products in the EU reached about €46.5 billion, yet organic food still represents only a modest share of total food sales in most Member States¹.

To reach 25% organic farmland by 2030, consumers must find organic easy to buy in everyday shopping: visible across categories, trusted, and affordable.

The typical organic consumer is concerned about the environment, health, and safety matters, and is less concerned about food prices². Efforts to grow the organic market mostly rely on information that appeals to the individual's motivation. Organic labels help inform choices if consumers know and have trust in the label³.

The European Commission offers funding for initiatives that promote EU agricultural products with EU quality labels. 90 organic product campaigns have been supported, covering many countries and products within but also outside the EU.

The European Commission's Vision for the Future of Agriculture and the EU Directive on empowering Consumers for Green Transition (EU 2024/825) highlight the need to enable consumers to make

Summary

- Strategies to boost demand for organic food rely on giving information to consumers and appealing to their motivation.
- Our experimental study reveals that availability and assortment are equally crucial for increasing organic choice.
- Competing marketing and sustainability messaging divert attention away from organic.
- Attractive organic offers are a key lever for increasing organic purchase.
- Policy and retailers need to address unsubstantiated sustainability claims that undermine organic demand.
- Different, substantiated sustainability claims need to be coordinated to avoid cannibalising on the organic market.
- The aim should be to make organic the easy default for everyday shopping - visible, trusted, and affordable.

¹ Willer H, Trávníček J, Schlatter, B (2025). *The World of Organic Agriculture 2025 Statistics and Emerging Trends*. Frick, Bonn: FiBL, IFOAM - Organics International. <https://orgprints.org/54617>.

² Leonidou, L. C., Eteokleous, P. P., Christofi, A.-M., & Korfiatis, N. (2022). Drivers, outcomes, and moderators of consumer intention to buy organic goods: Meta-analysis, implications, and future agenda. *Journal of Business Research*, 151, 339-354. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2022.06.027>

³ Macready, A. L., Hieke, S., Klimczuk-Kochańska, M., Szumiał, S., Wachter, K., Arnoult, M. H., Vranken, L., & Grunert, K. G. (2025). Why trust is crucial – The moderating role of trust in the relationship between motivation and intention to buy healthy, sustainable and novel foods. *Food Quality and Preference*, 126, 105386. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodqual.2024.105386>

informed sustainability choices and to tackle unfair commercial practices including misleading environmental claims (greenwashing).

Key findings

Consumer demand for organic is shaped by the motivation (why and how much they value organic), ability (understand, recognise, and afford organic) and opportunities (availability and how much organic stands out in the choice environment). Across Europe, studies consistently identify three practical conditions that increase organic purchasing: (1) organic options are available across everyday categories; (2) the EU organic logo is easy to spot and trusted; (3) consumers are not overloaded with competing sustainability claims⁴.

The choice architecture of the supermarket (assortment, placement, pricing, label clarity) strongly shapes whether organic products end up in the basket. The supermarket assortments are carefully curated and hinge on both strategic decisions and how products perform in sales, but there is less research quantifying the impact of this factor.⁵ To better understand its role, we investigated in the OrganicTargets4EU project how exactly the organic assortment and other aspects of the supermarket choice architecture influence organic food purchases. We tested these mechanisms in a simulated online supermarket visited repeatedly by consumers in Denmark, Germany, Italy, and Romania.

- When the organic assortment was expanded relative to conventional, organic choices increased to a similar level, even with a price premium.
- The repeated exposure to organic options in all product categories increased organic choices, over and above the mere availability effect.
- By contrast, adding other labels (e.g., climate labels, premium branding, or bestseller cues) did not strengthen organic choice—their presence on conventional products reduced organic choices.

Labels used in the supermarket experiment

EU organic	“EU” climate	Social norm nudge
Private-label premium brand	Private-label basic brand	Premium brand

⁴ Schleenbecker, R., & Hamm, U. (2013). Consumers’ perception of organic product characteristics: A review. *Appetite*, 71, 420-429. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.appet.2013.08.020>

⁵ Sadler, A., Moran, D., & Jaacks, L. (2024). Effectiveness of real-world marketing of organic foods and beverages: A systematic review of recent evidence. *PLOS Sustainability and Transformation*, 3(8), e0000123. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pstr.0000123>

This underlines the importance of availability, visibility, clarity, and repeated exposure. A sustainability label can increase consumer choices, but the marginal effect of additional labels is much smaller, and multi-label contexts can create confusion and sustainability trade-offs.⁶

Development needs and challenges

Meeting the organic growth targets requires a robust and predictable market for organic products. Information campaigns play a part, but evidence suggests that campaigns alone are not enough: policymakers and retailers also need to remove everyday barriers such as limited availability, higher prices, and confusion in a crowded label environment.⁴

Reaching more consumers and increasing consumer demand require improved availability of organic products and clear ways to identify them, both in retail and in catering outlets, as well as improved understanding and communication of the benefits of organic.

There is a need to strengthen trust and clarity of the EU organic logo with clear communication about robust control and the consistent use in retail environments. Misleading or overlapping sustainability claims (“label jungle”) can dilute organic messaging.

There is also a need to improve price transparency and affordability—e.g., entry-level organic price points, fair promotions, and fiscal tools such as lower VAT—where feasible.

Supermarkets can do more to make it easier for people to choose organics—for example by broadening range, improving what’s on the shelves, and using clearer labels and simple information or prompts (nudges) that guide shoppers’ choices⁷.

Policy recommendations

Policymakers can contribute to stimulating consumer demand for organic products as a strategic lever to reach ambitious goals for organic sector development. The aim should be to make organic the easy default for everyday shopping—visible, trusted, and affordable.

The EU Commission should protect and strengthen the EU organic logo by enforcing controls and curbing misleading environmental claims

- Publish practical guidance for using additional food sustainability labels alongside the EU organic logo in line with the empowering consumers to make sustainable choices and avoiding consumer confusion and trade-offs.
- Improve market and price transparency by monitoring organic price premiums and retail margins (e.g., via a market observatory) to support evidence-based action (see Policy Brief #10 Statistics).
- Developing guidance on combining the organic logo with national or regional identifiers and supporting research on the effectiveness of the compulsory EU/non-EU indications.

⁶ Sonntag, W. I., Lemken, D., Spiller, A., & Schulze, M. (2023). Welcome to the (label) jungle? Analysing how consumers deal with intra-sustainability label trade-offs on food. *Food Quality and Preference*, 104, 104746. <https://doi.org/https://doi.org/10.1016/j.foodqual.2022.104746>

⁷ Nudging Organic <https://demooisteboodschapisbio.be/wp-content/uploads/2025/04/Sustainable-Nudging-Report-2025-common.pdf>

The EU Commission should continue EU promotion funding to improve consumer recognition of and trust of organic and the EU organic logo

- Coordinating promotion campaigns for organic, specifically transnational organic products in different Member States and in collaboration with the private sector.
- Emphasising the significance of organic as the only EU regulated scheme for sustainable production with clear control and encourage education campaigns about the environmental and social benefits of organic food and farming.

The EU Commission should develop guidance on what claims can be used for organic and conventional products

- Ensure recognition of organic product attributes concerning health, climate, environment, and animal welfare using suitable methods that can differentiate between production systems.
- Enable consumers to compare reliably organic with other sustainability claims and labels to avoid greenwashing.

National and regional policymakers should support the private sector in improving the availability and visibility of organic food in retail and in catering outlets

- Encourage retailers to offer a wider range of organic choices as a strategy to increase the share of organic sales and improving visibility through distributed placement (including online), shelf markers and clear labelling, as well as branding and packaging.
- Introduce clear labelling rules for organic ingredients in public and hospitality catering (e.g., Denmark's catering label with gold, silver, and bronze statues).
- Use national and regional Organic Action Plans (see Policy Brief #13 Organic Action Plans) to implement these recommendations.

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Strengthening organic in AKIS

for better advice, training, and knowledge exchange

Introduction

Strengthening advice, mentoring, education, and training is essential for the sustainable growth of the organic sector. Organic farming requires a whole farm management approach, adapting practices to local conditions. Farmers depend on accessible, high-quality information, peer-to-peer learning, and organic expertise in well-functioning Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS), central to the successful conversion and long-term performance of organic farms.

EU initiatives-including SCAR-AKIS, EIP-AGRI, Horizon research, and the 2021 EU Organic Action Plan-stress knowledge exchange, interactive innovation, digital tools, and advisor training as important to foster a more resilient and innovative farming community. High-quality advice and skills development attract a new generation of future farmers and support sustainability transitions.

Member States are responsible for advisory services, AKIS implementation, and education systems. They must ensure that farmers have access to innovation and up-to-date knowledge and can leverage existing funding opportunities.

Advisory systems and training are core elements of AKIS in both the CAP Strategic Plans Regulation (EU 2021/2115) and proposals for the post-2027 CAP. Organic farming is mentioned as one agri-environmental and climate action for which Members States are encouraged to provide incentives. National CAP Strategic Plans often include conversion advice, demonstration activities, or Continuing Professional Development (CPD) support, but coverage and funding differ greatly. National Organic Action Plans frequently highlight training

Summary

This policy brief outlines findings related to organic in AKIS, such as advisory service and education activities, complemented by policy brief #9 Research and Innovation.

- Major gaps in quality and coverage of advice for organic exist. Organic knowledge is often shared in informal networks, peer to peer, and by organic farming associations. Organic is poorly integrated into formal education systems.
- Advisory systems and training are core elements of AKIS in the CAP. Organic farming is an agri-environmental action. Member States should provide support for farmers in this area through AKIS.
- Organic farming actors and activities need full integration and sustainable funding for AKIS, and farmers should have access to qualified and affordable advice on organic.
- This will create enabling conditions for conversion to organic, innovation, and public-good delivery.

needs, awareness raising, curriculum development, and support for advisory systems essential for organic expansion.

This policy brief complements policy brief #9 Research and Innovation, also part of AKIS.

Key findings

The [OrganicTargets4EU](#) project engaged with more than 300 advice and training stakeholders through national workshops and surveys, mainly in eight focus countries (Austria, Denmark, France, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, Romania). It carried out an analysis of support policies and national organic action plans. The results provide one of the most complete pictures to date of how organic advice, mentoring, and training function across EU Member States. We also considered reports of the ongoing OrganicAdviceNetwork project on Mapping advisory service providers for organic farming, an analysis of CAP and other funding sources supporting advice for organic and a mapping of educational pathways to become an advisor for organic in 13 Member States.¹

Major gaps in quality and coverage of advice for organic advisory support in the EU

Advisory systems for organic are highly uneven across the EU. There is no clear information on the number of advisors competent in organic agriculture in most countries, and training systems are inconsistent. Organic farmers often receive support through general advisory systems, which are uneven in quality and not consistently tailored to the specific knowledge needs of organic production.

Organic knowledge relies on informal networks and organic farming associations

Peer-to-peer exchanges and networks emerge as crucial knowledge engines. Organic farming associations are often the most trusted and competent providers of organic-specific information and in some cases advice. They also offer training, peer-to-peer exchange, field days and mentoring. They frequently are a bridge between farmers, researchers, and policymakers. Many help farmers connect with processors, supply chains, and consumers and support market development. However, they are rarely fully recognised or supported financially in the national AKIS.

Organic is poorly integrated into formal education

From vocational schools to universities, organic curricula are limited or absent in most Member States. As a result, new advisors often lack education and training in organic, whilst many have practical organic experience.

General advisory systems focus too narrowly on organic production

Farmers also need support on markets, financial management, climate resilience, soil health, digitalisation, and supply chains, but most systems provide only technical or administrative advice.

¹ See deliverable D1.1, 3.1 and 3.2 of at <https://www.organicadvicenetwork.eu/project-deliverables>

Policy recommendations

Organic farming is one climate and environment priority area in the CAP. Fully integrating and sustainably funding organic farming actors and activities in AKIS will create enabling conditions for conversion to organic, innovation, and public-good delivery—far beyond what scattered or project-based measures can achieve (see also policy brief #1 Drivers and Barriers).

Improve farmers' access to affordable and up-to-date advice on conversion and maintaining organic farming

- **EU policymakers:** Ensure that organic farming is explicitly embedded in AKIS and Farm Advisory Services in the CAP and develop a European database of qualified advisors competent in organics to improve transparency for farmers as part of the European Organic Action Plan.
- **National policymakers:** Using instruments of the CAP with clear budget allocations to promote specialised, affordable, and high-quality advice on organic farming. Encourage advice that integrates business planning, market access, digitalisation, and climate adaptation alongside technical production; carry out mapping of organic advice to create and maintain publicly accessible databases of qualified advisors; recognise and support organic farming associations as important AKIS stakeholders.
- **Organic farming associations and other NGOs:** Complement formal advisory systems through peer-to-peer support, mentoring, and capacity-building initiatives.

Improve training opportunities for advisors and other professionals and education in organic farming at all levels

- **EU policymakers:** Encourage the use of EU programmes (Erasmus+ and the Pact for Skills) to support training for advisors and professionals in organic farming and sharing of curricula and Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) (e.g., the as developed in the [OrganicAdviceNetwork](#) project) for vocational and higher education and support cross-border learning and exchange.
- **National level policymakers:** integrate organic farming (including some mandatory) into vocational and higher education, building on existing training programs to provide specialised knowledge for advisors and agricultural professionals and covering topics beyond production (e.g., markets, climate resilience, sustainability).
- **Organic and other NGOs:** Co-develop training programmes with educational institutions, ensuring accessibility for advisors and farmers and supporting lifelong learning pathways in organic.

Build and recognise peer-to-peer networks as core AKIS instruments

- **EU policymakers:** Peer-to-peer learning should be systematically supported through CAP interventions, EIP-AGRI, and Horizon Europe. Demonstration farms, communities of practice, field days, and conversion “one-stop shops” should be recognised as core AKIS tools.
- **National level policymakers:** Member States should support national and local farmer-led networks, including demonstration farms and learning clusters, and invest in digital platforms to enable exchange in remote areas. Organic organisations and NGOs play a key role in facilitating such networks that complement formal advisory systems.

Invest in European organic knowledge hubs, digital tools, and knowledge exchange initiatives in the context of the European Organic Action Plan

- **EU policymakers:** secure long-term funding for the European Organic Farm Knowledge Platform, ensuring integration with EUFarmBook and multilingual access and the integration of digital tools; promote cross-border networking for organic advisors and the establishment of organic innovation and competence centres (see also policy brief #12 Capacity building)
- **National level policymakers:** support national organic knowledge hubs with links to research, education, and advisory services, connecting actively to European platforms and networks and develop digital tools.
- **Organic and other NGOs:** host open-access knowledge hubs, organise cross-border exchanges, and translate research into practical tools for farmers and advisors.

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Katalin Szépkuthy Allacherné, ÖMKI

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Organic research and innovation: a strategic investment in Europe's agri-food systems

Introduction

The EU's ambition to build a resilient, competitive, and sustainable agri-food system depends on innovation that strengthens farm performance while restoring natural resources and supporting rural communities.

Organic farming plays a strategic role in this transition. It reduces dependency on external inputs, regenerates soils and biodiversity, and delivers system-based solutions that are increasingly taken up in agriculture. To sustain and scale these benefits, targeted research and innovation (R&I) is essential.

Organic farming faces distinct challenges that cannot be addressed through generic or purely technology-driven innovation pathways. Managing soil fertility, pests, and diseases without synthetic inputs, adapting to climate change, and strengthening organic value chains require knowledge-intensive, system-based solutions developed in close cooperation with farmers and other practitioners. Organic R&I has a long tradition of co-creation and on-farm experimentation, making it a valuable model for innovation delivery within Europe's Agricultural Knowledge and Innovation Systems (AKIS).

The EU's Vision for Agriculture and Food recognises the central role of R&I in delivering climate neutrality, biodiversity protection, food security, and viable rural livelihoods. Support is currently provided

Summary

- Research and innovation (R&I) in organic is strategic as a driver of Europe's resilience, competitiveness, and sustainability.
- Organic and agroecological R&I strengthens farm profitability, reduces dependency on external inputs, and regenerates natural capital. It delivers solutions that are taken up throughout the agricultural sector.
- However, organic R&I risks being diluted within broad sustainability agendas, not serving the specific needs of the organic sector. There is limited transparency on funding levels, weak coordination, and insufficient mechanisms to translate research results into practice.
- The next EU research and innovation framework (Horizon Europe), the European Competitiveness Fund, and a future EU Organic Action Plan will determine whether organic farming can continue to contribute effectively to EU priorities on climate and biodiversity, food security, rural vitality, and the competitiveness of the agri-food sector.
- Policymakers should ringfence funding and build capacity for organic R&I in Europe, broaden participation of farmers and practitioners, strengthen Europe's organic leadership through better coordination of organic research networks, and invest in long-term capacity for sharing and applying research results.

through Horizon Europe, the Common Agricultural Policy via AKIS and EIP-AGRI (part of the EU CAP Network), and national research programmes. The 2021 EU Organic Action Plan set a target of 30% of agri-food research funding for topics relevant to organic farming. A future Organic Action Plan provides an opportunity to reinforce this commitment and ensure coherence across EU and national instruments.

At a time of major policy transitions, including the preparation of the next EU Research & Innovation Framework Programme (Horizon Europe) and the European Competitiveness Fund, clear choices are required. Without targeted priorities and good coordination, organic R&I risks being diluted within broad sustainability agendas. With strategic support, it can remain a key lever for implementing the EU's Vision for Agriculture and Food and for strengthening Europe's leading role in this area.

Key findings

Research & innovation for organic farming makes a critical contribution to resilient, competitive, and sustainable food systems

Organic farming depends on knowledge-intensive, system-based innovation, yet several structural challenges limit the impact of public investment in organic R&I. EU and national programmes show that organic R&I delivers practical solutions, with benefits extending beyond the organic sector.

Broad research priorities of sustainability and agroecology dilute specific needs of organic

Current funding frameworks do not consistently address the specific needs of the organic sector. The shift towards broad thematic European Partnerships for sustainability under Horizon Europe has reduced the visibility of organic R&I and diluted efforts at the EU and national levels. Available information does not allow transparent assessment of whether funding targets set out in the EU Organic Action Plan are met.

Funding levels are not proportional to the growth ambitions for the organic sector

While most national Organic Action Plans include research priorities, funding is often not proportional to the size of or the ambition of the organic sector, and alignment with EU-level priorities remains weak. Results from applied research and innovation projects are insufficiently shared, limiting uptake by farmers and advisors. These findings point to a need for clearer priorities, better coordination, and stronger mechanisms to translate organic R&I into practice.

TP Organics identified 31 priority topics for organic and agroecology

The Strategic Research & Innovation Agenda (SRIA) of TP Organics, developed in close collaboration over two years in extensive bottom-up consultation involving farmers, researchers, and other stakeholders, proposes 31 priority topics under three themes that make up the vision of TP Organics: Leading for the environment, biodiversity and climate; leading for people, communities and sustainable livelihoods; and leading for responsible innovation.

Participation and coordination gaps reduce effectiveness

Farmers, advisors, and SMEs face barriers to accessing R&I funding, while weak coordination between EU projects, national programmes, EIP-AGRI Operational Groups, and other innovation initiatives leads to fragmentation.

A persistent gap between research and practice limits uptake

Insufficient resources are dedicated to preparing practice-oriented materials, maintaining knowledge platforms, and facilitating exchange across regions and languages. This includes also effective linking to AKIS at national level.

Policy recommendations

Funding for organic research and innovation and capacity building should be ringfenced and proportional to the growth ambitions of the sector. This strategic investment in the agri-food system delivers solutions to improve farm profitability, reduce input dependency, regenerate natural capital, and develop value chains.

At the EU level, including in any future EU Organic Action Plans, the European Commission should:

Secure dedicated funding for organic research and innovation in all funding instruments

- Allocate a minimum of 30% of agri-food R&I funding under Horizon Europe and the European Competitiveness Fund to projects specific to or highly relevant for organic farming.
- Include organic R&I as an explicit objective of policy window 1 (Clean Transition & Industrial Decarbonisation) and policy window 2 (Health, Biotech, Agriculture and Bioeconomy) in Horizon Europe and the European Competitiveness Fund
- Ring-fence funding for organic and agroecological R&I within relevant national programmes.
- Ensure transparent monitoring and reporting on how EU and national R&I funding addresses organic sector needs and policy targets.
- Align European Partnerships, missions, and national programmes to explicitly include organic research objectives.

Broaden participation in R&I projects through simplification of funding rules

- Design R&I calls that actively involve farmers, advisors, SMEs, NGOs, and value-chain actors through reinforced multi-actor approaches.
- Make two-stage procedures and simplified funding rules the standard for practice-oriented innovation.
- Expand the use of Financial Support to Third Parties to lower administrative barriers and enable experimentation in diverse regional contexts.
- Promote open science while safeguarding data rights and ensuring meaningful participation of practitioners in project governance.

Strengthen Europe's leadership through a coordinated organic research network in the EU Organic Action Plan

- Secure long-term support for a European network of national organic research funding bodies, building on the experience of CORE Organic.

- Use this network to align EU and national priorities, coordinate calls, and maintain strategic capacity in organic R&I.
- Anchor the network within the future EU Organic Action Plan to ensure continuity and policy coherence.

Encourage Member States to invest in specific organic research and innovation

- Allocate funding for specific organic projects and programmes in line with national and regional organic action plan priorities, including national contributions to joint European calls.
- Develop dedicated research and innovation capacities.
- Monitor how research funding is addressing organic needs at national and regional level and whether funding levels are adequate to achieve the targets set for the organic sector.

Invest in capacity for sharing and scaling research results

- Provide stable funding for European and national knowledge platforms and research archives relevant to organic farming.
- Support the development of practice-oriented materials, tools, and multilingual resources from all publicly funded organic R&I.
- Facilitate exchange through networks, conferences, and training opportunities, particularly for early-career researchers and practitioners.
- Strengthen links between research, advisory services, and innovation support within AKIS.

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Ivana Trkulja, International Centre for Research in Organic Food Systems (ICROFS)

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Does organic count? Better statistics and market data

Introduction

Organic farming is one of the fastest growing sectors in food and agriculture and has been for the last 30 years. With EU organic land area doubling and retail sales trebling every decade, more than 18 million ha (11% of EU agricultural area) were organic and the EU retail market for organic reached €50 billion in 2024.¹

This growth, and organic farming's potential to deliver environmental and market outcomes, depends on timely, quality data critical for:

- Market transparency and efficiency, including fair pricing
- Farmer decisions to convert to, and remain in, organic farming
- Food businesses to engage and invest in processing, distribution, and trade
- Implementation and evaluation of policy support, including setting payment rates

Statistics and market data are a fundamental cornerstone of organic sector development. Without timely and quality data, decision-makers—farmers, food businesses, investors, policymakers, and consumers—are flying blind. Many will be unwilling to take the risks or will make mistakes, diminishing the environmental and market benefits that organic farming delivers.

Summary

- Statistics and market data are a cornerstone of organic development. Farmer and food business decisions to engage with and invest in organic, as well as policy implementation and evaluation, all rely on timely and quality organic data.
- With the sector approaching 20-25% of EU agriculture, there should be an organic equivalent for all agricultural and food statistics.
- Significant progress has been made in recent years with respect to crop areas and livestock numbers using administrative and statistical sources. However, major gaps and challenges exist for production, farm finance, market, trade, and environmental sustainability data.
- Improvements in the SAIO Regulation implementation and the representation of organic farms in FSDN are critical.
- EU digitalisation and data governance proposals provide new opportunities. Unique IDs and EU Business Wallets could facilitate data exchange between organic operators, control bodies, and authorities, improving data collation and analysis.

¹ World of Organic Agriculture 2026 <https://www.organic-world.net/yearbook/yearbook-2026.html>

Figure 1 Overview of key organic food and farming statistics in the EU²

Organic Agriculture in the European Union 2024

Key findings

The OrganicTargets4EU project examined the implications of reaching 25% of EU farmland organic by 2030. We analysed historical trends, future growth projections, and modelled the production, economic, and environmental impacts. We used data on organic crop areas, livestock numbers, input use, yields, retail sales value, and exports, often at regional level.

Our work confirmed the findings of earlier projects: organic statistics and market data are still far from fit for purpose. Some aspects have improved, notably Eurostat's agricultural census data, with the inclusion of organic identifiers for individual farms and relevant variables.

Moving the legislative basis for organic data, from the EU organic regulations to the SAIO Regulation (2022/2379) on agricultural statistics, however, is not leading to better organic data as promised. Key variables on crops in conversion and organic livestock were dropped and data for policy evaluation were focussed on the use of plant protection products. These concerns were also raised by the European Court of Auditors in their 2024 report on organic farming policy.

The Farm Sustainability Data Network (FSDN, formerly FADN) collates farm financial and physical data and some sustainability indicators. Organic farming identifiers allow specific data to be extracted. In many countries organic sample sizes are small, key farm types are missing, and the representativeness of the organic sector is questionable.

Market data on prices, quantities, retail and out-of-home catering sales, and trade are frequently absent. Available data often rely on commercial providers, organic organisations, or national agencies such as Agence Bio (FR) or AMI (DE). European level collation is limited, with the World of Organic Agriculture² a notable exception, alongside the Commission's Marketing and Analytical Briefs³.

² World of Organic Agriculture 2026 <https://www.organic-world.net/yearbook/yearbook-2026.html>

³ EU Organic Market and Analytical Briefs: https://agriculture.ec.europa.eu/data-and-analysis/sustainability-and-organic-farming/agricultural-markets-organic-sector_en

Development needs and challenges

Previous projects with a direct focus on organic market data, such as EISfOM (2003-2006) and OrganicDataNetwork (2012-14),⁴ made detailed recommendations for improving organic market data—many still not implemented. From these and the current project, key areas are:

Production data: Farm and crop areas and livestock numbers are readily available from agricultural censuses and surveys, public administration (IACS), and certification data. There is a need to reduce the duplicate reporting burden on farmers and to streamline data exchange with authorities consistent with data protection requirements. The reduced data availability since the implementation of the SAIO Regulation needs urgent resolution.

Farm financial data, including inputs and outputs, are obtainable from the Farm Sustainability Data Network (FSDN). The problems with small samples, missing farm types and overall representativity of organic samples identified in the project need to be addressed. This may be possible through over-sampling organic farms and adjusting their weighting in aggregate reporting.

Market data are poorly covered across many countries and at EU level. Collaborating with commercial providers, organic organisations and public agencies—ideally through market observatories—would improve coverage and consistency. Timeliness is critical for business decisions, including farmer conversion responses to market slowdowns or recovery.

Trade data within the EU and for exports from the EU are largely absent, making supply balance assessments in support of market development or certification difficult. Import data has improved with the use of Traces and organic shipment certificates. Other countries, including the US, have included an organic identifier digit into the Harmonised System for trade data, an approach which could also be implemented in the EU.

Environmental sustainability data: Research studies provide solid evidence that organic farming makes a positive contribution to environmental sustainability, but they are often site-specific and difficult to extrapolate to wider scales. The proposed Farm Sustainability Compass, with appropriate indicators and quality data, could enable meaningful regional to EU-level benchmarking and policy evaluation.

Digitalisation and data governance provide opportunities for better organic data availability and use including from the potentially data rich certification process. Commission proposals for data governance authorities, unique business IDs and the European Business Wallet could facilitate a better exchange of data between businesses, control bodies and public authorities, and improve statistical collation and analysis.

Policy recommendations

In the long-term, with the organic sector approaching 20-25% of EU agriculture, the **overall aim** should be to ensure there is an organic equivalent for all agricultural and food statistics.

⁴ OrganicDataNetwork project: <https://www.organicdatanetwork.net/home.html>

The EU Commission should prioritise improving the collection, availability, and reporting of organic data, including adapting the relevant legal frameworks, by:

- Reviewing the implementation of the SAIO Regulation to restore conversion, livestock, and other data losses, and to address inconsistencies between the various Implementing Regulations.
- Improving trade data availability, also for the internal market, by including an organic identification digit in the Harmonised System codes.
- Establishing an EU Market Observatory for organic market data and encourage related national and regional initiatives in Member States.
- Improving the availability and representativeness of organic farming data in FSDN.
- Including organic-specific environmental sustainability data and research evidence in sustainability benchmarking and the planned Farm Sustainability Compass tool.
- Improving data exchange between organic businesses, control bodies, and public authorities by integrating organic requirements in digitalisation, data governance authorities, unique business IDs, and the European Business Wallet initiatives proposed by the Commission.

Member States should prioritise improving the collection, availability, and reporting of data, by:

- Improving the quality of data and representativity of organic farms in national FSDN datasets.
- Partnering with businesses, commercial data providers and organic sector organisations on national organic market observatories for reliable market data.
- Improving yield and product output data via organic identifiers in crop yield and harvest estimates.
- Ensuring full representation of organic in national statistical reporting, market forecasting, policy modelling, and evaluation activities.

Further information

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Nicolas Lampkin, Thünen Institute, January 2026

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Strengthening organic aquaculture in Europe

Introduction

The aquaculture sector in Europe is still far from reaching its full potential in terms of growth and meeting the increasing demand for more sustainable seafood. The EU imports over 80% of the seafood that it consumes. Aquaculture products overall (including imports) represent 30% of EU consumption of seafood, while EU aquaculture products represent only 10% of EU consumption.¹

Although, in principle, existing policy frameworks i.e. the Common Fisheries Policy (CFP), the European Maritime, Fisheries, and Aquaculture Fund (EMFAF), the Green Deal, the Farm to Fork Strategy, and the Multi-annual National Strategic Plans for Aquaculture provide support for organic aquaculture, available data on the actual support provided is rather scarce. This problem was also identified in the European Court of Auditors' report on organic farming support.

The European Commission has encouraged Member States to include the development of organic aquaculture among the objectives of their Multi-annual National Strategic Plans (NSPAs) for sustainable aquaculture 2021-2030. Nevertheless, the analysis of the status of organic aquaculture seems poorly developed in their plans. Countries seem to pay more attention to other forms of sustainable production, rather than organic aquaculture. This is evident from the limited emphasis placed on identifying objectives and activities that specifically promote the development of organic aquaculture, when contrasted with the efforts

Summary

This policy brief outlines key factors shaping organic aquaculture development in the EU.

Organic aquaculture is still at an early stage of development in many countries, and its situation is fragile. The enterprises are sensitive to input availability and costs (especially feed and juveniles), as well as market demand and prices, and production and processing systems can be capital intensive. Technical knowledge and market and policy engagement are critical. In most cases, it is not possible to integrate aquaculture systems within broader farming systems to capitalise on synergies and provide a buffer in challenging circumstances.

This is why, among the most urgent issues, it is necessary to:

- Review the most pressing challenges currently faced by organic producers, in particular the lack of organic juveniles and organic feed.
- Provide organic support payments to compensate for higher input costs (feed, juveniles, equipment investment) and necessary support for the transition to organic aquaculture.
- Streamline licensing and spatial planning frameworks, including accelerated procedures for certified organic aquaculture projects and designating specific zones for organic aquaculture within Maritime Spatial Planning (MSP) frameworks.

¹ EUMOFA (2022) The EU Fish Market. 2022 Edition. European Market Observatory for Fisheries and Aquaculture Products. https://www.eumofa.eu/documents/20178/521182/EFM2022_EN.pdf.

allocated to the analysis and promotion of conventional aquaculture.

A further element of concern derives from the Commission's choice, as part of the EU's long-term budget for 2028-2034, not to present a separate fund to support the Common Fisheries Policy (CFP). Instead, support for fisheries, aquaculture, and ocean-related activities would be integrated into a single, larger fund that also covers other areas, such as cohesion and agriculture. The loss of the dedicated EMFAF fund, through the integration of fisheries and aquaculture support into broader national programmes, coupled with the considerable autonomy granted to Member States in designing their national measures, risks weakening the uniformity and traceability of fisheries and aquaculture related spending, including support for organic aquaculture.

Key findings

A quantitative systematic literature review was conducted in the OrganicTargets4EU project, with the aim of identifying and analysing the factors that either constrain or support the development of European organic aquaculture, including technical, business, and policy issues.²The overall search strategy was based on the PRISMA protocol, including both peer-reviewed articles and grey literature. The review focuses on the species most farmed in European organic aquaculture: Atlantic salmon, rainbow trout, common carp, European sea bass, gilthead seabream and shellfish. The top six constraining factors identified were:

- Perceived feasibility of organic aquaculture from the farmers' perspective
- Price difference between organic and conventional products for consumers
- Availability and costs of organically produced inputs (e.g., juveniles, feed)
- Level of bureaucratic complexity and applicability of organic aquaculture rules
- Consumer awareness and knowledge about organic aquaculture and product added value
- Availability of incentives (support payments and investment aids)

After two rounds of Delphi interviews with a panel of experts (i.e., consultants, researchers, processors, and retailers), the following key areas of the food supply chain were highlighted to promote key strategies for the growth of the organic aquaculture market in Europe in the coming years:

- Technical/regulatory barriers
- Selling prices and production costs
- Boosting organic food in out of home catering

The Multi-annual National Strategic Plans examined do not contain any objectives for the development of **Knowledge and Innovation Systems (KIS)** for organic aquaculture or only mention general objectives, without any specific organisational aspects. Interviews and online surveys with aquaculture experts led to the following suggestions for the development of organic aquaculture KIS:

- Establish specific units on organic aquaculture in national and regional governmental bodies to support regulation and planning

² Toomey L, Alfonso S, Carbonara P, Jahrl I, Mente E, Lampkin N, Lembo G (2025) Unlocking the potential of organic aquaculture in the EU: a review of policy support and supporting and constraining factors. *Reviews Aquaculture* 17(4): e70089, <https://doi.org/10.1111/raq.70089>.

- Provide allocated funds addressing KIS development for organic aquaculture
- Foster the development of a practice-oriented research system, together with a multi-stakeholder engagement process to facilitate effective knowledge transfer
- Establish mechanisms to feed research results to advisory system, training, and education

The main results of the project were discussed with stakeholders from several EU countries at an aquaculture workshop held on-line in May 2025 to validate findings through feedback on the main topics addressed by the project, specifically on:

- production systems: barriers, constraints and future trends;
- policy support for organic aquaculture production;
- supply chain development;
- consumer demand;
- knowledge and innovation systems;
- research and Innovation.

Participants considered the most relevant constraining factor to the development of organic aquaculture the availability and cost of organically produced inputs, followed by the price gap between organic and conventional products.

Developing innovations to improve the impact of aquaculture on nature and environment, as well as developing alternative feeds using proteins of non-animal origin, were identified as important factors. The three key recommendations were:

- Facilitate the provision of organic eggs and juveniles,
- Develop effective marketing strategies to stimulate growth in the sector
- Promote financial incentives.

Policy recommendations

To build organic aquaculture up to the same status and importance for EU sustainability outcomes as organic farming, we recommend that:

At EU level, as part of the current review of organic regulations, develop smarter, more flexible organic aquaculture regulations, by:

- Reviewing the most pressing regulatory challenges currently faced by organic producers, in particular the lack of organic juveniles and of organic feed. Amendments to the regulations should be discussed in the context of the current availability of certified hatcheries and alternative proteins or ingredients for the formulation of organic feeds. The interpretation of

EU organic rules should be aligned across all Member States and control bodies to minimise uncertainty for producers.

At national level, incentivise organic producers, as land-based producers, by:

- Providing organic support payments to compensate for higher input costs (feed, juveniles, equipment investment) and the transition to organic aquaculture. Equivalent measures to those for organic farming in the proposed CAP Regulation 2028-2034 should be included in the Common Fisheries Policy proposals. Member States should integrate funded, measurable organic aquaculture targets into both national aquaculture plans and organic action plans.
- Establishing specific units on organic aquaculture within national and regional governmental bodies to support regulation and planning, including streamlining licensing and spatial planning frameworks, including accelerated procedures for certified organic aquaculture projects and designating specific zones for organic aquaculture within Maritime Spatial Planning frameworks.

At national level, support organic aquaculture supply chain development and consumer demand, by:

- Collaborating with **supermarket chains and other retailers** to establish dedicated organic aquaculture product lines, incorporating storytelling and branding, to further raise consumer awareness.
- Using **public procurement** to include organic seafood products in school canteens, hospitals, and public catering outlets, creating stable demand and raising consumer awareness.

At EU and national level, invest in research and innovation and associated advisory and dissemination facilities, by:

- Allocating a proportion of the EMFAF or the forthcoming EU Research and Innovation Framework Programme (as well as national funds) to **dedicated research and innovation in organic aquaculture** and supporting the development of **organic aquaculture knowledge and innovation systems**, including advice, mentoring, training, research, statistics and market data, and the development of institutional capacities and peer-to-peer networks or operational groups linked to public-sector institutions and organic sector organisations.

Further information

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Giuseppe Lembo and Lola Toomey, Fondazione COISPA ETS, Italy, January 2026

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Organic action plans:

Integrating policies, building capacity, acting locally

Introduction

Organic farming pursues multiple goals with a systems approach. Combined with many policy support measures, this can make policymaking difficult. The dual focus on public and market goods, highlighted in the first EU Organic Action Plan (2004), requires co-ordination between units with sometimes dissimilar aims.

A strong focus on supply-push environmental support measures, such as organic conversion and maintenance payments, can have a negative impact on organic markets. Too strong a demand-pull market focus can undermine environmental delivery.

Organic action plans (OAPs) have the potential to integrate public good and market-oriented, supply-push and demand-pull policies, and ensure coherence with broader policy frameworks. This needs to be supported by effective targets (see policy brief #3), stakeholder engagement, clearly defined development needs, and dedicated resources and co-ordination capacity (Meredith et al., 2018). A broad range of production, market and information, as well as capacity building measures can be included.

The focus is often on EU-level or national OAPs, but regional or local (bio-district or city level) plans are also valuable and can be more responsive to specific local needs.

Key findings

The [OrganicTargets4EU](#) project identified that almost all EU Member States had developed OAPs for the current period (2023 to 2027/30, see Figure 1, green bars), many as a response to the EU OAP recommendations. Only Spain and Lithuania did not do so. Ireland and Luxembourg renewed their plans in 2025 (Figure 1, yellow bars). Some countries have a track record of multiple older OAPs going back as far as 1995 (Figure 1, grey bars with number of plans).

Summary

- Organic action plans, adopted in almost all EU Member States, are important for the integration of public good and market policies, supply-push and demand-pull policies, as well as coherence with the CAP, rural development, and planned National and Regional Partnership Plans.
- A wide range of production, market, and information policies are included in OAPs, with opportunities to do more for capacity-building and local initiatives such as bio-districts and bio-cities.
- The current EU Organic Action Plan plays an important role in guiding MS organic policies in the context of national CAP strategic plans. This needs to be extended to the next CAP and NRP programming period with a revised EU organic action plan.
- The quality of OAPs can be improved with more attention to evaluation, identification of development needs, stakeholder engagement and adequate resourcing of core actions.

Figure 1: Periods covered by EU and national organic action plans since first introduced in 1995

Source: Lampkin et al. (2024) updated¹

The project analysed the current OAPs in terms of content and compared with previous action plans (Figure 1, blue bars). 13 categories of actions in three broad groups were identified:

- **Production:** Organic and environmental support payments, investment aids.
- **Markets:** Producer groups and supply chains, public procurement, agritourism and gastronomy, exports and trade fairs, logos and branding, certification and regulations.
- **Information:** Consumer information, advice and demonstration, training and education, research and innovation, statistics and market data.

In most cases, both the introduction of new plans and the developments from previous plans represented a step forward in organic policymaking. However, some weaknesses were also identified, including lack of evaluations of previous plans, lack of status quo analyses and specification of sector development needs, lack of stakeholder involvement, and lack of dedicated funding and co-ordination frameworks, at least for the core delivery of the action plans. Similar issues were also raised by the European Court of Auditors in their 2024 review of organic policies.

Development needs and challenges

The project's analysis of current and previous OAPs, and discussions with stakeholders in national backcasting and policy workshops, highlighted some specific development needs that should be considered in future organic action planning.

Better action plans

While there are many good examples of OAPs, e.g., Czechia, Denmark, and Germany, some would benefit from improvement in scope and process. An analysis of the impacts of previous plans and the specific, local development needs of the organic sector is critical. Duplication of actions in the EU OAP does not necessarily address local needs. Stakeholder involvement at all stages—design,

¹ The current plans for FR and GR and new plans (yellow) for IR and LU were not analysed in the original deliverable but have been integrated in the updated national organic sector factsheets available at: <https://organictargets.eu/organic-sector-factsheets/>

implementation, and evaluation—is strongly encouraged. Resources (financial and staffing) need to be allocated to at least the core elements and co-ordination of the plans, even if other funding programmes are used to support individual actions. Monitoring and evaluation frameworks with appropriate indicators and data need to be implemented from the outset.

Capacity building

In several parts of the project, the need for long-term funding for institutional (public and organic sector) capacity building has been highlighted. Examples include information platforms, advisory networks, research institutions, university departments, market observatories, centres of excellence, and policy engagement capacity of the organic sector. Such capacity building has occasionally featured in OAPs but should have a much stronger focus in future plans.

Bio-districts—acting locally

Regional OAPs are common in many countries, e.g., Germany, Italy, Spain. The bio-district idea, promoted as part of the current (2021) EU OAP, takes these a stage further, with a specific focus on local businesses and public authorities working together to support public procurement, short supply chains, gastronomy and agritourism, and by encouraging local consumer engagement. Networks of bio-districts and bio-cities in Italy, Germany, the Netherlands, and elsewhere are emerging to support this process. Active encouragement of such local initiatives is highly desirable.

EU Organic Action Plans

Previous EU OAPs tended to focus mainly on actions (e.g., events, regulatory changes) that could be undertaken by the Commission itself. The introduction of national CAP Strategic Plans gave the current EU OAP more of a focus on guiding and supporting Member State actions. In preparation for the next CAP and the National and Regional Partnership (NRP) Plans for 2028-2034, there is a need for a revised and updated EU OAP, taking account of all the policy recommendations from the OrganicTargets4EU project.

Policy recommendations

Organic action plans including capacity building and bio-districts have proven value in the organic policy context. They should continue to be encouraged as a means of integrating supply-push and demand-pull policies, and public good and market-oriented policies, consistent with organic farming's multi-functional, systemic approach. As an **overall aim**, OAPs at EU, national, regional, and local level should be reviewed, strengthened, and extended to encompass the next CAP and NRP programming period (2028-2034), ensuring good policy integration and coherence.

The EU Commission should review and strengthen the current EU Organic Action Plan in the context of the proposals for the next CAP, by:

- conducting an evaluation of the outcomes so far, as well as surveys of farmer attitudes to conversion and value chain actors, to see what lessons can be learned for the next phase.
- identifying actions that would support improved policy implementation and co-ordination by Member States, for example between national organic research funders.

The EU Commission should support Member States in improving the quality, scope, implementation, and evaluation of national organic action plans, by:

- assessing how well national OAPs are integrated with CAP Strategic plans and other policies.
- establishing a network for sharing best practice OAP examples and guidance between MSs, supported by the EU CAP Network and organic policy experts.
- encouraging capacity building, using existing initiatives for producer groups, farm advisory services, EIP operational groups and extending these to cover other areas.
- exploring options for an EU-level organic market observatory.
- encouraging networks of relevant institutions and organisations to share best practice and co-operate in different fields, supported through other funding mechanisms where feasible.

Member States should review and strengthen their national and regional action plans, including bio-districts and cities, with a 2034/2035 horizon by:

- ensuring coherence and integration with NRP and CAP plans for 2028-34.
- defining meaningful production, market and environmental targets, based on previous OAP evaluations, sector status quo analyses, and clear definition of sector development needs, including opportunities for generational renewal and administrative simplification.
- integrating institutional (public and organic sector) capacity building elements, with resources to ensure long-term delivery of organic-specific initiatives.
- including private sector involvement in delivery, e.g., partnerships with organic organisations, businesses, market data companies, universities and charities.
- committing resources (financial and staff-time) to the core elements and co-ordination.
- engaging stakeholders at all stages (design, implementation and evaluation), including support for organic organisations to develop policy engagement capacity.
- ensuring processes for monitoring and evaluation, including relevant indicators and data sources, are included from the outset.

Further information

Lampkin N, Lembo G & Rehburg P (2024). *Assessment of agricultural and aquaculture policy responses to the organic F2F targets*. Deliverable D1.2 OrganicTargets4EU. IFOAM Organics Europe. <https://orgprints.org/id/eprint/52716/>

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OrganicTargets4EU national organic sector factsheets <https://organictargets.eu/organic-sector-factsheets/>

OrganicTargets4EU policy briefs: <https://organictargets.eu/policy-briefs/>

Nicolas Lampkin, Thünen Institute, December 2025

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